

21GRD03 PaRaMetriC

D4: Report on the validated reference techniques used for emittance and reflectance measurements of PRC materials in the spectral range 0.25 μm – 50 μm , with a target uncertainty below 3 % for emissivity and absorptivity

Lead participant for the deliverable: **PTB**

Due date of the deliverable: 30/09/2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 30/09/2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

Deliverable Cover Sheet

METROLOGY PARTNERSHIP

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

Glossary

IR	Infrared
PRCF	Passive Radiative Cooling foil
STW	sky transparency window
PRC	Passive Radiative Cooling
BRDF	Bidirectional reflectance distribution function
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared spectrometer
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PRT	platinum resistance thermometer
GUM	Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement
ITS-90	International Temperature Scale
UV/VIS/NIR	Ultraviolet/Visible/Near Infrared
FIRMOS	Far-Infrared Radiation Mobile Observation System
NESR	Noise-Equivalent Spectral Radiance
BB	Blackbody
BoPET	Biaxially Oriented Polyethylene Terephthalate
PT100	Resistance Temperature Detector
DTGS	Deuterated Triglycine Sulfate
PDRC	Passive Daytime Radiative Cooling
InGaAs	Indium Gallium Arsenide
SRM	Standard Reference Material

TABLE OF CONTENTS

21GRD03 PaRaMetriC.....	1
1 Introduction.....	5
2 Overview of the selected PRC benchmark materials.....	6
3 Measurement methods	7
3.1 Reference technique at PTB	7
3.1.1 Uncertainty budget estimation.....	8
3.1.2 Results of PTB.....	8
3.1.3 Additional PRC materials measured at PTB.....	11
3.1.4 Summary	11
3.2 Measurement techniques at LNE	12
3.2.1 Reference measurement technique using a calorimetric principle.....	12
3.2.2 Uncertainty budget estimation.....	14
3.3 Measurement technique at CAE.....	15
3.3.1 Design and measurement principle.....	15
3.3.2 Results of CAE	18
3.3.3 Uncertainty budget estimation.....	23
3.4 Measurement techniques at CNR	24
3.4.1 Design and measurement principle.....	24
3.5 Measurement technique at DFM	29
3.5.1 Design and measurement principle.....	29
3.5.2 Uncertainty budget estimation.....	30
3.6 Measurement technique at FIW	32
3.6.1 Design and measurement principle.....	32
3.6.2 Aging	32
3.6.3 Uncertainty budget estimation.....	35
3.6.4 Results.....	35
3.7 Measurement techniques at Aalto.....	39
3.7.1 Design and measurement principle.....	39
3.7.2 Uncertainty budget estimation.....	41
3.8 Measurement techniques at TUBITAK	43
3.8.1 Design and measurement principle.....	43

3.9	Measurement techniques at IO-CSIC.....	46
3.9.1	Design and measurement.....	46
3.9.2	Uncertainty budget estimation.....	47
3.10	Measurement techniques at IETcc-CSIC	48
3.10.1	Design and measurement principle.....	48
3.10.2	Uncertainty budget estimation	51
3.11	Measurement techniques at NKUA	52
3.11.1	Design and measurement principle.....	52
3.11.2	Uncertainty budget estimation	54
4	Comparative analysis in the MIR range.....	55
4.1	3M R&D PRCF Foil.....	55
4.2	SPACECOOL.....	59
4.3	V98RF.....	62
4.4	Conclusions for the IR range.....	65
5	Comparative analysis in the Solar range.....	66
5.1	3M R&D PRCF Foil.....	66
5.2	SPACECOOL.....	68
5.3	V98RF.....	70
5.4	Conclusions for the Solar range	71
6	Conclusions	72
7	References	74

1 Introduction

The aim of this task was to perform characterisations of and comparisons between reference and end-user measurement techniques (from participants) applied for measurement of the reflectance and emittance of selected PRC materials in the broad spectral range from 250 nm to 50 μm encompassing both the solar spectrum (250 nm – 2500 nm) and the infrared transparency window of the atmosphere (8 μm – 13 μm). In a second step, samples of a PRC material selected to serve as a benchmark material were provided to establish the traceability of participants' measurement techniques. Measurement results obtained by participants were compared to determine the measurement techniques and procedures appropriate for characterising the radiative properties of PRC materials. Furthermore, the performance of the in-field measurement instruments (e.g. portable emissometers) calibrated with the benchmark samples were assessed. Task 3.1 also provided data on the radiative properties of PRC materials to WP2 and WP4.

One of the main challenges lies in the precision of available measurement methods and the broad spectral range required. Measurements typically need to span wavelengths from 250 nm to 50 μm , depending on the intended application. PRC materials reflect strongly within the solar range (250–2500 nm) and emit efficiently within the infrared window (around 7.1–13 μm). Also, for thermal modelling and energy balance assessments, total hemispherical emissivity is critical, whereas angular spectral emissivity profiles serve as key indicators when evaluating new materials.

Many PRC materials utilize optically structured or multilayered coatings, introducing added complexity due to their heterogeneous composition [1]. This makes achieving accurate measurements more difficult and increases uncertainty. Moreover, unlike smooth and opaque surfaces, PRC materials often exhibit distinctive angular emissivity behaviors. Some recent studies have emphasized that accounting for full angular emissivity, often neglected in past experimental work, is essential for assessing net cooling power, especially under high humidity or elevated temperature conditions [2].

The Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) [3], Germany's national metrology institute, is leading this work package. Together with the PaRaMetriC consortium, the precise and traceable methodologies to quantify the optical properties of PRC materials, including reflectance and emissivity across the full 250 nm to 50 μm range, targeting a standard uncertainty below 0.03, were developed. Several benchmark PRC materials have been identified and were characterized by various project partners using different techniques.

This work package also aims to study the long-term durability of PRC materials by monitoring changes in their optical properties due to environmental factors like heat, moisture, contamination, and aging. Achieving this requires highly accurate emissivity and reflectivity measurements with minimal uncertainty. Additionally, new methodologies were developed to convert directional emissivity values, commonly provided by field instruments, into hemispherical total emissivity (D5). This conversion is vital for accurate simulations and thermal analyses. By supplying high-quality hemispherical emissivity data, PaRaMetriC partners contributed to a more robust framework for evaluating the performance of PRC materials in practical applications.

2 Overview of the selected PRC benchmark materials

Within the project, several stakeholders and companies already involved in energy-efficient building envelopes and traditional cool roof systems, or who are working towards the development and commercialization of actual PRC materials, were contacted for a preliminary evaluation of their products. Three samples have been selected (Figure 1): SPACECOOL, V98RF and 3M R&D PRCF Foil. All samples are PFAS-free. In addition, several other materials and paints were investigated (see Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 1: Photo of the selected PRC materials: SPACECOOL, V98RF and 3M R&D PRCF Foil.

SPACECOOL

A self-adhesive multilayer silver-polymer optical film with specular reflection and surface roughness-induced light scattering from the company SPACECOOL INC. was applied to a copper substrate with a diameter of 50 mm and a thickness of 5 mm. The substrate includes a hole of 2 mm diameter to accommodate a platinum resistance thermometer (PRT), facilitating the monitoring of the substrate temperature.

"V98RF" of Cooling Photonics S.L. and Almecc Group

A selective emitting polymer "RF" developed by Cooling Photonics was applied on a silver-based mirror labeled "Vega 98®" (V98) cut to size 40 mm x 40 mm provided by Almecc Group. "Vega 98®" is a specially designed highly reflective surface. It consists in a high-purity aluminium substrate, enhanced by a specific PVD multilayer coating system based on silver. Vega 98 is manufactured on a continuous coil vacuum coating plant, which makes it a fully scalable product. The RF coating preserves the high reflectivity of the V98 substrate while providing high emissivity in the IR atmospheric window, resulting in a high-performance selective emitter (V98RF).

3M R&D PRCF

A self-adhesive metal-free white-diffuse R&D developmental passive radiative cooling foil (PRCF) provided by 3M was adhered on an aluminum substrate of 90 mm in diameter using a thermal paste Apiezon. A 2 mm hole for the PRT was also provided in the substrate.

3 Measurement methods

3.1 Reference technique at PTB

PTB operates two specialized and complementary facilities designed for angular-resolved measurements of directional spectral, directional total, and hemispherical total emissivity, both in air and vacuum conditions. These facilities span a broad spectral range from 1.4 μm to 200 μm and can accommodate sample temperatures from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ up to $1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The Emissivity Measurements in Air Facility (EMAF) [4] and the Reduced Background Calibration Facility (RBCF 2) [5] have been in operation for several years at PTB and have supported numerous national and international research projects. Notable among these are EURAMET-funded initiatives such as *VITCEA* ("Inspection Techniques for Composites in Energy Applications"), *EMIRIM* („Improvement of emissivity measurements on reflective insulation materials), and the *MetEOC* (Metrology for Earth Observation and Climate) series, spanning from *MetEOC* 1 to 4. Additionally, these facilities have played a vital role in supporting key climate observation missions like ESA's *FORUM* [6] and NASA's *Libera* [7].

The facilities have also been involved in multiple national and international intercomparison exercises [8], and have provided tailored measurement services for external partners through bilateral collaborations and contract-based work.

In both systems, the emissivity determination relies on comparing the spectral radiance of the test sample with that of two calibrated blackbody sources at different temperatures, utilizing a Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer (see Fig. 2). The sample is heated and positioned within a thermally stabilized spherical enclosure. An analytical model, accounting for radiative heat flux balance at the sample surface and multiple internal reflections, is applied to precisely determine both the sample's surface temperature and its directional spectral emissivity [9].

To derive hemispherical total emissivity, a validated computational approach developed at PTB is employed. The angular dependence of directional emissivity is modeled as a weighted sum of the Fresnel reflectance components for both polarization states, incorporating the complex refractive index along with an empirical offset. This model is fitted to experimental data gathered from directional total emissivity measurements at discrete viewing angles: 10° , 20° , 30° , 40° , 50° , 60° , and 70° , including the corresponding uncertainty contributions. The final hemispherical emissivity is obtained by integrating the fitted model across the full angular range (0° – 90°) [4]. The emissivity measurements of the PRC materials were carried out using the EMAF setup.

Figure 2: Photo of the facility for emissivity measurement at PTB: two reference blackbodies and a temperature-stabilised spherical enclosure can be seen. The sample is mounted on a heater and placed inside the spherical enclosure.

3.1.1 Uncertainty budget estimation

The uncertainty of the directional spectral emissivity at PTB is calculated via a Monte–Carlo method, which is based on the complete radiation budget. This method considers every radiation contribution in the optical path and is spectrally dependent. Furthermore, the uncertainty budget is calculated for each individual measurement, as the significance of individual uncertainty contributions varies significantly depending on the conditions of the measurement and the sample investigated.

3.1.2 Results of PTB

Figure 3 presents the directional spectral emissivity of the three selected PRC materials measured at an observation angle of 10° from the surface normal. The red dashed line marks the boundaries of the infrared atmospheric window and also outlines an ideal emissivity profile typical of a selective PRC material. The measurements were carried out at sample temperatures between 60°C and 100°C , with slight adjustments based on each material's thermal stability. This temperature variation has no significant impact on the results, as the emissivity of these materials remains stable within this range.

For the spectral range between $1.4\ \mu\text{m}$ and $5\ \mu\text{m}$, the directional–hemispherical reflectance is shown in the form of "1 - reflectivity." These reflectance measurements were performed at room temperature, since the integrating sphere configuration does not require heating of the sample.

Across all samples, the measured emissivity curves display sufficiently high emissivity within the infrared atmospheric window, although with some spectral features. A clear drop in emissivity is observed in the shorter infrared region (below $6\ \mu\text{m}$). As previously discussed, the cooling efficiency of PRC materials depends not only on their strong emission within the IR window but also on their high reflectance in the solar spectral range ($250\text{--}2500\ \text{nm}$). Assuming that the reflectivity continues to be high, comparable to the levels measured near $1.4\ \mu\text{m}$, the evaluated materials show considerable potential for passive radiative cooling applications. Nevertheless, this assumption requires verification through measurements in the solar spectrum (Section 5).

Figure 3: Directional spectral emissivity of three selected PRC materials measured at PTB: shown at an observation angle of 10° with respect to the surface normal and in the range from $1.4\ \mu\text{m}$ to $25\ \mu\text{m}$. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement shown as shaded areas around the curves.

The integrated emissivity values, both directional total and hemispherical total, for all tested PRC materials are presented in Table 1 and visualized in Figure 4. The associated uncertainties represent standard measurement

uncertainties with a coverage factor of $k = 1$, determined in accordance with the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM)*. For assessing radiative cooling performance in the infrared, the integration was performed over the primary atmospheric transparency window, from $7.1 \mu\text{m}$ to $13 \mu\text{m}$.

The results show that the directional total emissivities of the PRC materials, along with their associated uncertainties, are consistently high. As expected, emissivity values tend to decrease slightly with increasing observation angle.

Table 1: Directional total and hemispherical total emissivities of four selected PRC materials in the wavelength range from $7.1 \mu\text{m}$ to $13 \mu\text{m}$ with corresponding standard uncertainties $u(\epsilon)$.

Angle	SPACECOOL ϵ (60 °C)	$u(\epsilon)$ $k=1$	V98RF ϵ (100 °C)	$u(\epsilon)$ $k=1$	3M R&D PRCF Foil ϵ (60 °C)	$u(\epsilon)$ $k=1$
10°	0.928	0.015	0.891	0.008	0.901	0.008
20°	0.933	0.014	0.889	0.008	0.898	0.008
30°	0.935	0.014	0.884	0.008	0.900	0.008
40°	0.935	0.014	0.878	0.008	0.899	0.008
50°	0.927	0.014	0.878	0.008	0.885	0.008
60°	0.899	0.015	0.856	0.008	0.846	0.009
70°	0.818	0.015	0.730	0.009	0.753	0.010
ϵ hem	0.889	0.015	0.834	0.008	0.846	0.009

Figure 4: Directional total emissivities of three selected PRC materials in the wavelength range from $7.1 \mu\text{m}$ to $13 \mu\text{m}$ with corresponding standard uncertainties depending on the angles of observation from 10° to 70° with respect to the surface normal.

The significance of long-wavelength emission in PRC materials lies not only in the presence of an additional atmospheric transmission window around 20 μm , which may contribute modestly to enhanced cooling, but also in the potential benefits of broadband thermal emission in the 25–40 μm range [11]. This becomes particularly relevant in many practical applications of PRC materials - such as thermal management of heat pumps, electronics, building surfaces, and photovoltaic modules - where the materials often operate at above-ambient temperatures due to air contact and self-heating. Under such conditions, PRC materials can function effectively as broadband long-wave infrared emitters.

To maximize cooling efficiency, it is advantageous for the emissivity of PRC coatings to remain high not only within the main atmospheric window from 7.1 to 13 μm , but also across the longer wavelength region up to 50 μm . However, it should be noted that radiation beyond 13 μm is largely absorbed by water vapor and the surrounding atmosphere, meaning that enhanced emissivity in this range is primarily beneficial in cold and dry environments. In contrast, under warm or humid conditions, high emissivity beyond 13 μm may be counterproductive, as the emitted energy is more likely to be reabsorbed locally rather than radiated to space.

Due to PTB’s capability to perform traceable far-infrared (FIR) emissivity measurements linked to the International Temperature Scale ITS-90, it was possible to characterize the studied PRC coatings in this extended spectral domain. The resulting emissivity spectra, covering wavelengths up to 50 μm , are presented in Figure 5, extending the measurements previously shown in Figure 3 into the FIR region. Notably, two out of the three PRC materials display high emissivity in the 13–50 μm range, indicating their strong potential for additional cooling functionality when operating in colder environments.

Additionally, in the first phase of the project, three other materials developed by 3M company and eight commercially available PRC white paints were measured at PTB facility with the target uncertainties less than 3 % (Figure 6 and 7).

Figure 5: Directional spectral emissivities of three selected PRC materials in the FIR range extending the data presented in Figure 3: shown at one angle of observation of 10° with respect to the surface normal and in the range up to 50 μm . The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown as shaded areas around the curves.

3.1.3 Additional PRC materials measured at PTB

Figure 6: Directional spectral emissivities of three additional PRC materials of 3M company shown at one angle of observation of 10° with respect to the surface normal and in the range from 1.3 μm to 25 μm. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown as shaded areas around the curves.

Figure 7: Directional spectral emissivities of eight commercially available PRC white paints shown at one angle of observation of 10° with respect to the surface normal and in the range from 1.3 μm to 25 μm. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown as shaded areas around the curves.

3.1.4 Summary

Within the first phase of PaRaMetriC project, PTB has determined the emissivity of various modern, commercially available PRC materials and coatings in the wavelength range from 5 μm to 50 μm under various angles of observation ranging from 10° to 70°. These measurements achieved an absolute uncertainty of less than 0.016 for the SPACECOOL sample and less than 0.010 for the other two samples- Cooling Photonics and R&D developmental PRCF from 3M Company. These uncertainties are traceable to the International Temperature Scale ITS-90. Thus, this result surpasses the stated uncertainty target of 0.03, providing a valuable reference that will help improve the emissivity results of other project partners. The integrated quantities- directional total and hemispherical total emissivity- were calculated within the range of the main IR atmospheric window approximately from 7.1 μm to 13 μm. Additionally, the directional-hemispherical spectral reflectivity was measured using an integrating sphere from 1.4 μm to 5 μm.

3.2 Measurement techniques at LNE

3.2.1 Reference measurement technique using a calorimetric principle

Calorimetric technique: direct measurement of the radiation power produced by two-disc shape samples heated uniformly toward a blackbody at 78K.

The principle of measurement was presented in [12]. The size of the samples was increased during the JRP project 16NRM06 EMIRIM (2017-2020) in order to increase the radiation flux emitted by the samples and to relatively reduce the parasitical heat fluxes.

Figure 8: Cross-section view of the sample heater with the two samples and the thermal guard

An improvement of the sample heating system was done during PaRaMetriC project. Add of two copper plates with a thickness of 5 mm, one on each side of each electrical heating resistor (sample section and thermal guard section), to homogenize the temperature generated by the electrical heating resistor. New copper plates with a thickness of 5 mm to hold the temperature sensors and with good flatness to ensure good thermal contact with the rear sides of the samples. The temperature sensors for the control and measurements of the temperatures in the sample heater were replaced.

Figure 9: View of the heater with the three TA6V connecting parts between the copper disc and the copper ring

Figure 10: Parts constituting the sample heating section of the heating system and samples

Table 2: Main features of the new sample heater

Samples diameter	100 mm
Radiating area of the 2 samples	0.01571m ²
Thickness of the samples	5 mm for EMIRIM project
External diameter of the thermal guard	165 mm
Width of the gap between the samples and the guard rings	0.1 mm
Heat transfer coefficient between the samples section and the thermal guard section	0.04 W K ⁻¹

3.2.2 Uncertainty budget estimation

The assessment of uncertainty was described in detail in reference [12]. The uncertainty budget was updated for the new configuration. The uncertainty sources considered are given in tables 2, 3 and 4 giving the uncertainty budgets for measurement of the nominal total hemispherical emissivities 0.02, 0.05 and 0.97. The nominal values of the parameters sources of uncertainty are given in the second columns of the tables and the standard uncertainty on the value of the parameters are given in the third columns. The expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) on the measured total hemispherical emissivity due specifically to each parameter is given in the fourth columns of the tables.

Table 3: Budget of uncertainty for measurement of a total hemispherical emissivity of 0.97

Parameter or model	Value of the parameter	Standard uncertainty (k = 1)	Induced expanded uncertainty on the measured emissivity (k=2)
Area of the samples	0.015708 m ²	3.14 . 10 ⁻⁵ m ²	0.004
Area of the chamber walls	1.36014 m ²	0.06 m ²	9.3 . 10 ⁻⁵
Area of the samples rings	0.03218 m ²	8.10 ⁻⁵ m ²	5.2 . 10 ⁻⁷
Mean total hemispherical emissivity of the chamber walls	0.92	0.025	7.1 . 10 ⁻⁴
Mean total hemispherical emissivity of the guard rings	0.05	0.02	8 . 10 ⁻⁵
Electrical power	7.3219 W	7.7 10 ⁻⁴ W	2.1 . 10 ⁻⁴
Mean surface temperature of the samples	30.00 °C	0.6 °C	0.0155
Mean temperature of the chamber walls	77.36 K	1 K	4.3 . 10 ⁻⁴
Mean surface temperature of the rings	30.00 °C	1 °C	2.6 . 10 ⁻⁶
Edge heat loss by radiation	0.01498 W	0.0038 W	0.001
Edge heat loss by conduction between the samples section and the thermal guard section	0.000 W	0.040 W	0.011
Heat loss by air remaining in the chamber	0.0426 W	0.022 W	0.0057
Model used for emissivity calculation	-	2.5 . 10 ⁻⁵	0.001
Random variations of measured emissivities	0	0.001	0.003
Measured Emissivity	0.97	0.010	0.020

3.3 Measurement technique at CAE

3.3.1 Design and measurement principle

Determination of the spectral near-normal emittance using an integrating sphere setup

For determining the spectral near-normal emissivity ε_λ or absorptance α_λ , respectively, the spectral directional-hemispherical reflectance R_{dh} near-normal to the surface has been measured using an integrating sphere setup. For the solar spectral region an integrating sphere with an interior polytetrafluoroethylene surface and an UV/VIS/NIR diffraction spectrometer has been used. For the MIR wavelength range an integrating sphere with an interior gold surface and a FTIR spectrometer has been used. A schematic drawing of the setup for determining the spectral directional-hemispherical reflectance R_{dh} with a FTIR spectrometer is depicted on the left in Figure 11. The sample is tilted by an angle of 8° in order to cover the specular reflected part of the radiation as well as the diffusely reflected part. On the right in Figure 11 three different configurations are shown, which are used for measuring (one sample measurement and two reference measurements):

- the intensity reflected by the sample I_S (top right), denoted as sample measurement,
- the background intensity reflected by the gold reference I_B (middle right), denoted as the background measurement and
- the underground intensity without sample or gold reference I_U (bottom right), denoted as the underground measurement.

From these measurements, the spectral directional-hemispherical reflectance R_{dh} near-normal to the surface can be derived using the following procedure.

The measured intensity of the background I_B as a function of the wavelength λ can be derived as a function of the intensity of the incoming beam I_0 and the reflectance of the gold standard R_G :

$$I_B(\lambda) = I_0(\lambda) \cdot R_G(\lambda) \cdot \frac{(f_G + f_S) \cdot R_G(\lambda)}{1 - (f_G + f_S) \cdot R_G(\lambda)} \quad (1)$$

f_G represents the ratio of the gold coated area within the integrating sphere to the total sphere area, whereas f_S gives the ratio of the sample or gold standard area (visible from inside the integrating sphere) to the total sphere area. For the derivation of Eq. (1) the geometric progression has been used. The standard used as reference and the inner side of the integrating sphere have an identical gold coating and surface roughness (Infragold®). Therefore, both have the same reflectance R_G . The measured intensity of the underground I_U as a function of wavelength λ can also be derived in dependence on the intensity of the incoming beam I_0 and the reflectance of the gold standard R_G :

$$I_U(\lambda) = I_0(\lambda) \cdot x(\lambda) \cdot R_G(\lambda) \cdot \frac{f_G \cdot R_G(\lambda)}{1 - f_G \cdot R_G(\lambda)} \quad (2)$$

In ideal setups x would vanish, but in real setups x normally lies above zero.

From the intensities of the background I_B and the underground I_U an apparent reflectance of the underground R_U (which is not a sample or material property) can be defined as ratio of both:

$$R_U(\lambda) = \frac{I_U(\lambda)}{I_B(\lambda)} = x(\lambda) \cdot \frac{f_G}{f_G + f_S} \cdot \frac{1 - [f_G + f_S] \cdot R_G(\lambda)}{1 - f_G \cdot R_G(\lambda)} \quad (3)$$

and leads to an equation for x :

$$x(\lambda) = R_U(\lambda) \cdot \frac{f_G + f_S}{f_G} \cdot \frac{1 - f_G \cdot R_G(\lambda)}{1 - [f_G + f_S] \cdot R_G(\lambda)} \quad (4)$$

Finally the intensity reflected by the sample I_S can be derived as a function of the unknown reflectance of the sample R_S :

$$I_S(\lambda) = I_0(\lambda) \cdot \{x(\lambda) \cdot R_G(\lambda) + [1 - x(\lambda)] \cdot R_S(\lambda)\} \cdot \frac{f_G \cdot R_G(\lambda) + f_S \cdot R_S(\lambda)}{1 - [f_G \cdot R_G(\lambda) + f_S \cdot R_S(\lambda)]} \quad (5)$$

This leads to an equation for the measured reflectance R_{meas} :

$$R_{meas}(\lambda) = \frac{I_S(\lambda)}{I_B(\lambda)} = \frac{x(\lambda) \cdot R_G(\lambda) + [1 - x(\lambda)] \cdot R_S(\lambda)}{\frac{R_G(\lambda)}{1 - (f_G + f_S) \cdot R_G(\lambda)}} \cdot \frac{f_G \cdot R_G(\lambda) + f_S \cdot R_S(\lambda)}{1 - [f_G \cdot R_G(\lambda) + f_S \cdot R_S(\lambda)]} \quad (6)$$

Solving Eq. (6) for the reflectance of the sample R_S leads to a more complex equation:

$$\begin{aligned} R_S(\lambda) \\ = R_G(\lambda) \\ \frac{-f_G \cdot [1 - f \cdot R_G(\lambda)] \cdot [1 - x(\lambda)] - f_S \cdot \{f \cdot R_G(\lambda) \cdot [R_{meas}(\lambda) - x(\lambda)] + x(\lambda)\} + \sqrt{\{f_G \cdot [1 - f \cdot R_G(\lambda)] \cdot}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

with $f = f_G + f_S$. $x(\lambda)$ is given by Eq. (4).

The dependency of the spectral reflectance R_S of the sample on the parameters R_G , R_U , R_{meas} , f_G and f_S is obvious:

$$R_S = R_S(R_G, R_U, R_{meas}, f_G, f_S, \lambda) \quad (8)$$

Finally, the spectral reflectance R_S of the sample equals the spectral directional-hemispherical reflectance R_{dh} of the sample near-normal to the surface:

$$R_{dh}(\lambda) = R_S(\lambda) \quad (9)$$

A similar procedure can be performed for the solar spectral region. In the solar spectral region, an UV/VIS/NIR diffraction-spectrometer is used together with an integrating, which exhibits an interior polytetrafluoroethylene surface, specifically a Spectralon® coating (Figure 2). Furthermore, a dual-beam technique is used, where a reference is measured simultaneously to the sample. Nevertheless, an additional background measurement with a Spectralon® reference placed at the sample position and an underground measurement without sample or Spectralon® reference are needed for calibration.

Figure 11: Left: Sketch of a FTIR spectrometer with an external gold coated integrating sphere for the mid-infrared (MIR). Right: Integrating sphere setups for measuring the sample (top), the background with gold reference (middle) and the underground without sample or gold reference (bottom).

Figure 12: Dual-beam setup with polytetrafluoroethylene coated integrating sphere for measuring the spectral directional-hemispherical reflectance R_{dh} near-normal to the surface.

Due to Kirchhoff's law the spectral near-normal emissivity ϵ_λ equals the spectral near-normal absorptance α_λ :

$$\alpha_\lambda = \epsilon_\lambda \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, spectral near-normal emissivity ε_λ and the spectral near-normal absorptance α_λ of opaque samples with vanishing spectral directional-hemispherical transmittance T_{dh} can be calculated from the spectral directional-hemispherical reflectance R_{dh} near-normal to the surface:

$$\alpha_\lambda = \varepsilon_\lambda = 1 - R_{dh} \quad \text{for} \quad T_{dh} = 0 \quad . \quad (11)$$

Determining the total near-normal emissivity and total hemispherical emissivity

The total near-normal emissivity ε_n gives the total amount of thermal radiation that is emitted or absorbed by the surface nearly perpendicular to its orientation. The total near-normal emissivity ε_n with respect to the temperature T can be calculated by integrating the spectral near-normal emissivity ε_λ over all wavelengths with the Planck-function $I_{bb,\lambda}(T)$ as a weight function:

$$\varepsilon_n(T) = \frac{\int_{2 \mu m}^{35 \mu m} \varepsilon_\lambda(T) \cdot I_{bb,\lambda}(T) \cdot d\lambda}{\int_{2 \mu m}^{35 \mu m} I_{bb,\lambda}(T) \cdot d\lambda} \quad . \quad (12)$$

The Planck-function $I_{bb,\lambda}(T)$ gives the spectral intensity emitted by a black body at a certain temperature T . The calculations are done in accordance with DIN EN 12898.

Finally, the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h can be calculated from the total near-normal emissivity ε_n following the formula given in DIN EN 12898:

$$\varepsilon_h = 1.1887 \cdot \varepsilon_n - 0.4967 \cdot \varepsilon_n^2 + 0.2452 \cdot \varepsilon_n^3 \quad . \quad (13)$$

Furthermore, these calculations can be performed for other wavelengths ranges, such as $4 \mu m \dots 5 \mu m$, $5 \mu m \dots 10.5 \mu m$, $8 \mu m \dots 13 \mu m$ and $10.5 \mu m \dots 21 \mu m$, for comparing results with other setups and detectors and for determining the emissivity in the atmospheric infrared window.

Determining the solar absorptance

The solar absorptance α_{solar} is calculated by integrating the spectral near-normal absorptance α_λ over all wavelengths with the solar radiation onto the soil I_{solar} as weight function:

$$\alpha_{solar} = \frac{\int_{0.3 \mu m}^{2.5 \mu m} \alpha_\lambda \cdot I_{solar}(\lambda) \cdot d\lambda}{\int_{0.3 \mu m}^{2.5 \mu m} I_{solar}(\lambda) \cdot d\lambda} \quad . \quad (14)$$

The calculations are done in accordance with DIN EN 410.

3.3.2 Results of CAE

At CAE samples from 3M, Spacecool and Alemco/Cooling Photonics have been characterized among other samples. Photos of the sample, which have been prepared and provided by PTB for the measurements at CAE, are shown in Figure 13.

The resulting spectral near-normal emissivity ε_λ of these samples is depicted in Figure 14 for 3M R&D PRCF, in Figure 15 for Spacecool and in Figure 16 for V98RF in the wavelength range from $0.25 \mu m (= 250 \text{ nm})$ to $35 \mu m (= 35000 \text{ nm})$.

Figure 13: Photos of the samples, which have been prepared and provided by PTB for the measurements at CAE. Top left: 3M R&D PRCF on aluminum substrate. Top right: Spacecool on aluminum substrate. Bottom left: Spacecool as free-standing foil. Bottom right: V98RF (aluminum substrate from Almeco with foil from Cooling Photonics).

Figure 14: Spectral near-normal emissivity ϵ_λ of the 3M R&D PRCF samples (large sample and small sample from Figure 13) in dependence on the wavelength λ from 0.25 μm (= 250 nm) to 35 μm (= 35000 nm). The expanded standard uncertainties are plotted as dotted lines.

Figure 15: Spectral near-normal emissivity ϵ_λ of the Spacecool samples (large sample, small sample and foil sample from Figure 13) in dependence on the wavelength λ from 0.25 μm (= 250 nm) to 35 μm (= 35000 nm). The expanded standard uncertainties are plotted as dotted lines.

Figure 16: Spectral near-normal emissivity ϵ_λ of the V98RF samples (large sample and small samples from Figure 13) in dependence on the wavelength λ from 0.25 μm (= 250 nm) to 35 μm (= 35000 nm). The expanded standard uncertainties are plotted as dotted lines.

Additionally the calculated total near-normal emissivity ϵ_n and total hemispherical emissivity ϵ_h are given in Table 4 whereas the solar absorptance α_{solar} is listed in Table 5.

Table 4: Resulting total near-normal emissivity ϵ_n and total hemispherical emissivity ϵ_h determined at CAE in the wavelength range from 2 μm to 35 μm .

sample	total near-normal emissivity ϵ_n	total hemispherical emissivity ϵ_h
3M R&D PRCF large sample	0.908 \pm 0.024	0.853 \pm 0.028
3M R&D PRCF small sample	0.901 \pm 0.024	0.847 \pm 0.028
Spacecool large sample	0.886 \pm 0.024	0.834 \pm 0.028
Spacecool small sample	0.881 \pm 0.024	0.830 \pm 0.028
Spacecool free-standing foil sample	0.882 \pm 0.024	0.830 \pm 0.028
V98RF sample 1 (small sample)	0.675 \pm 0.024	0.652 \pm 0.028
V98RF sample 2 (small sample)	0.680 \pm 0.024	0.655 \pm 0.028
V98RF sample 3 (large sample)	0.681 \pm 0.024	0.657 \pm 0.028

Table 5: Resulting solar absorptance α_{solar} determined at CAE.

sample	solar absorptance α_{solar}
3M R&D PRCF large sample	0.095 \pm 0.024
3M R&D PRCF small sample	0.096 \pm 0.024
Spacecool large sample	0.077 \pm 0.024
Spacecool small sample	0.082 \pm 0.024
Spacecool free-standing foil sample	0.100 \pm 0.024
V98RF sample 1 (small sample)	0.036 \pm 0.024
V98RF sample 2 (small sample)	0.042 \pm 0.024
V98RF sample 3 (large sample)	0.033 \pm 0.024

For comparing results with other setups and detectors and for determining the emissivity in the atmospheric infrared window the calculated near-normal emissivity ε_n has also been calculated for limited wavelength bands, such as 4 μm ... 5 μm , 5 μm ... 10.5 μm , 8 μm ... 13 μm and 10.5 μm ... 21 μm . The resulting values are presented in Table 3 and Table 4.

Table 6: Near-normal emissivity ε_n for limited wavelength bands (4 μm - 5 μm and 5 μm - 10.5 μm).

sample	wavelength band: 8 μm ... 13 μm	wavelength band: 10.5 μm ... 21 μm
3M R&D PRCF large sample	0.929 \pm 0.024	0.879 \pm 0.024
3M R&D PRCF small sample	0.929 \pm 0.024	0.865 \pm 0.024
Spacecool large sample	0.927 \pm 0.024	0.875 \pm 0.024
Spacecool small sample	0.926 \pm 0.024	0.867 \pm 0.024
Spacecool free-standing foil sample	0.925 \pm 0.024	0.868 \pm 0.024
V98RF sample 1 (small sample)	0.885 \pm 0.024	0.622 \pm 0.024
V98RF sample 2 (small sample)	0.887 \pm 0.024	0.628 \pm 0.024
V98RF sample 3 (large sample)	0.889 \pm 0.024	0.630 \pm 0.024

Table 7: Near-normal emissivity ε_n for limited wavelength bands (8 μm - 13 μm and 10.5 μm - 21 μm).

sample	wavelength band: 4 μm ... 5 μm	wavelength band: 5 μm ... 10.5 μm
3M R&D PRCF large sample	0.579 \pm 0.024	0.933 \pm 0.024
3M R&D PRCF small sample	0.576 \pm 0.024	0.933 \pm 0.024
Spacecool large sample	0.406 \pm 0.024	0.933 \pm 0.024
Spacecool small sample	0.404 \pm 0.024	0.933 \pm 0.024
Spacecool free-standing foil sample	0.408 \pm 0.024	0.931 \pm 0.024
V98RF sample 1 (small sample)	0.128 \pm 0.024	0.821 \pm 0.024

V98RF sample 2 (small sample)	0.136 ± 0.024	0.824 ± 0.024
V98RF sample 3 (large sample)	0.135 ± 0.024	0.826 ± 0.024

3.3.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

The main factors which influence the uncertainty of the measured reflectance are:

- Standard: The uncertainty of the standard, which influences the reference measurement.
- Underground: Uncertainty of the underground signal, which influences the underground measurement.
- Spectrometer: Uncertainty of the detected intensity signal.
- Ratio sample and sphere area: Uncertainty of the geometry, which influences the radiation distribution inside the integrating sphere.
- Ratio gold and sphere area: Uncertainty of the geometry, which influences the radiation distribution inside the integrating sphere.
- Spectrometer: Further influences onto the calibration and stability of the spectrometer

Additional uncertainties occur when calculating the total near-normal emissivity ε_n from the spectral near-normal emissivity ε_λ due to the limited wavelength range and when calculating the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h from the total near-normal emissivity ε_n due to the lump assumption about the angular dependency.

Finally, the absolute expanded standard uncertainty $U_{R_s} = k \cdot u_{R_s}$ for a coverage factor $k = 2$ of the sample reflectance R_s can be derived using the law of propagation of uncertainties:

$$U_{R_s}(R_G, R_U, R_{meas}, f_G, f_S) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial R_s}{\partial R_G}\right)^2 \cdot U_{R_G}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R_s}{\partial R_U}\right)^2 \cdot U_{R_U}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R_s}{\partial R_{meas}}\right)^2 \cdot U_{R_{meas}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R_s}{\partial f_G}\right)^2 \cdot U_{f_G}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R_s}{\partial f_S}\right)^2 \cdot U_{f_S}^2} \quad (15)$$

Finally, the calculation of the spectral near normal emissivity ε_λ or absorptivity α_λ can be made for opaque samples using Eq. (11). Furthermore, the total near-normal emissivity ε_n and the total hemispherical emissivity ε_h have been calculated using Eq. (12) and Eq. (13). Finally, the solar absorptance α_{solar} has been calculated by Eq. (14).

The expanded standard uncertainty of the spectral values has been derived to ± 0.020 , whereas the expanded standard uncertainty of the total near-normal values has been determined to be ± 0.024 , whereas the expanded standard uncertainty of the total hemispherical values is ± 0.028 .

3.4 Measurement techniques at CNR

3.4.1 Design and measurement principle

CNR operates the Far-Infrared Radiation Mobile Observation System (FIRMOS), a Fourier Transform Spectrometer working in the far- and mid-infrared range [13]. FIRMOS was designed and built in-house by CNR-INO. It serves as a versatile instrument for both laboratory studies and field campaigns. It has been employed during the implementation phase of the ESA FORUM mission [6], participating in measurement campaigns that include ground-based observations of the atmosphere and surface [14],[15], as well as deployments on stratospheric balloon platforms [16],[17].

Table 8: FIRMOS characteristics.

Configuration	Mach-Zehnder (double input, double output)
Spectral coverage	100–1600 cm ⁻¹ (6.25–100 μm)
Spectral resolution	0.3 cm ⁻¹ (max 0.25)
Beam aperture (field of view)	22.4 mrad

The calibration of the spectra is performed by alternating views of the target and of two black bodies (BB) as described in [18].

Measurements of samples were carried out both in the laboratory and outdoors.

Laboratory measurements

The sample was placed at the entrance of the instrument. The temperature of the sample was measured using a PT100 sensor. The instrument was thermally stabilised at a fixed temperature. Several PT100 and Dallas sensors monitored the temperature of various parts and subsystems of the instrument. All the temperature values are acquired synchronously with the spectral measurements.

Table 9: Laboratory measurements. The temperature values reported (see the two right-most columns) represent the average and the standard deviation over the measurement period.

sample	date	duration	n. I1 spectra	T sample stabilised	Firmos stabilised	Tsample (°C)	T_FIRMOS (°C D1, D10)
Spacecool	26 Mar 2024	5.5h	34	no	yes (24°C)	20.04±2.49	24.71±0.55, 24.72±0.70
Spacecool	26 Mar 2024	8.5h	52	no	yes (32°C)	20.34±2.08	30.70±1.31, 30.87±1.41
3M R&D PRCF	27 Mar 2024	3h	20	no	yes (24°C)	19.86±3.36	24.91±0.23, 24.89±0.64
3M R&D PRCF	27 Mar 2024	4h	35	no	yes (32°C)	20.12±3.12	31.05±0.26, 31.22±0.63
Cooling Photonics V1	8 May 2024	15.5h	93	no	yes (32°C)	22.26±1.94	31.60±0.19, 31.76±0.38

FIRMOS and the sample can be stabilized at different temperatures to enhance the contrast of the signal. In the case of the laboratory measurements (see, Table 9), the sample was left at room temperature, and two settings were adopted for the instrument.

Figure 17: measurement setup in the laboratory.

The emissivity estimation relies on the following equations:

$$L_s^\uparrow = \epsilon B(T_s) + (1 - \epsilon)L^\downarrow \quad (16)$$

Where L_s^\uparrow is the radiance measured by FIRMOS, $B(T_s)$ is the Planck emission at the sample temperature T_s . We assume the radiance exiting the instrument L^\downarrow and reflected towards the detector can be modeled as that of a black body at an effective temperature (T_e) where T_e is the average temperature of the detectors.

$$L_s^\uparrow = \epsilon B(T_s) + (1 - \epsilon)B(T_e) \quad (17)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{L_s^\uparrow - B(T_s)}{B(T_s) - B(T_e)} \quad (18)$$

The sample's directional spectral emissivity was derived applying Eq. 18 to individual level 1c spectra. FIRMOS level 1c data are the NESR-weighted average of single-scan spectra (level 1b) sharing the same calibration acquisitions (Bianchini, 2019).

The sample temperature T_s and the effective temperature T_e were averaged over the 4-minute duration of each measurement.

Figure 18 shows the results of the three samples. Absorption due to water vapour is visible in the emissivity values above 1400 cm^{-1} below roughly 400 cm^{-1} ; the spectral range between 1100 and 1300 cm^{-1} shows sharp features due to the BoPET beam splitter substrate.

It was therefore deemed more appropriate to deliver data filtered based on atmospheric transparency. The transmission of the atmosphere was simulated using the LBLRTM radiative transfer model [19], considering the average temperature and humidity values in the laboratory. The spectral range affected by BoPET-absorption was also filtered. Figure 18, shows the result after filtering.

Note: the denominator in Eq. 18 tends to zero for values below 200 cm^{-1} , for the temperatures used in this setup, since the radiance emitted by black bodies at those temperatures is nearly equivalent.

Figure 18: Filtered normal spectral emissivity for the three samples, blue: space cool, orange: 3M R&D PRCF, green: Cooling Photonics V1. The shading indicates uncertainty.

Field measurements

Measurements were carried out on the roof of Building B in the CNR Florence research area. When conducting field measurements, the sample was placed at a distance of 1 m from FIRMOS and the viewing zenith angle was 13° . The measurement sequence alternated between sample views and observations of the atmosphere (at 167° VZA) interspersed with views of the calibration BBs.

Table 10 summarizes some information about the sessions.

Since in open-air conditions the sample temperature may vary rapidly—due, for example, to wind—Level 1b data were used to estimate emissivity during subsequent data processing.

Although noisier than Level 1c data, Level 1b spectra have a measurement duration of approximately one minute, during which the sample temperature can be considered stable.

Figure 19: Field measurement setup.

Table 10: Field measurements.

sample	date	duration	n. spectra (I1b)	T sample stabilised	T_sample (°C)	Firmos stabilised	T_FIRMOS (°C D1, D10)
3M R&D PRCF	30 Jan 2024	2.5h 12:11–14:41	64 32 nad + 32 zen	yes	30.67±1.06	yes (24°C)	24.35±0.08, 24.43±0.60
Spacecool	30 Jan 2024	1.6h 15:08–16:58	48 24 nad + 24 zen	yes	31.62±0.43	yes (24°C)	24.28±0.20, 24.33±0.59

Table 11: Atmospheric conditions for 30 Jan 2024. Data from the LAMMA weather station positioned approximately 150 m from the location of the measurements. See: Consorzio LAMMA.

time	p/hPa	T/°C	R/%
12:00	1033	6	60
13:00	1032	9	50
14:00	1031	11	40
15:00	1031	12	35

16:00	1031	12	35
17:00	1031	12	40

We used LBLRTM to calculate the atmospheric transmission (τ) and emission (E) between the FIRMOS detectors and the sample, using as input the atmospheric conditions measured by a weather station located approximately 150 meters away (see Table 11). Spectral emissivity was calculated following the method described in [20].

$$L_{surf}^{\uparrow} = \epsilon B(T_s) + (1 - \epsilon)L_{surf}^{\downarrow} \quad (19)$$

$$L_{FIRMOS}^{\uparrow} = \tau L_{surf}^{\uparrow} + E^{\uparrow} \quad (20)$$

$$L_{surf}^{\downarrow} = \tau L_{FIRMOS}^{\downarrow} + E^{\downarrow} \quad (21)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{L_{FIRMOS}^{\uparrow} - \tau^2 L_{FIRMOS}^{\downarrow} - \tau E^{\downarrow} - E^{\uparrow}}{\tau(B(T_s) - L_{FIRMOS}^{\downarrow} - E^{\downarrow})} \quad (22)$$

Where τ is the transmission of the atmospheric layer between the sample and FIRMOS; $E^{\uparrow} = E^{\downarrow} = B(T_{air})$ is the emission from the layer, modeled as blackbody radiation at the air temperature; L_{FIRMOS}^{\uparrow} is the upwelling spectral radiance measured by FIRMOS in quasi-nadir-looking geometry; L_{FIRMOS}^{\downarrow} is the downwelling atmospheric spectral radiance measured by FIRMOS.

Equations Eq. 19—Eq. 22 assume specular reflection. If the surface is Lambertian, the angular-integrated downwelling radiance can be approximated by a single effective incidence angle (typically between 55° 60°). In this case the equations are modified as follows:

$$L_{surf}^{\downarrow} = \tau_{eff} L_{FIRMOS,eff}^{\downarrow} + E_{eff}^{\downarrow} \quad (23)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{L_{FIRMOS}^{\uparrow} - \tau_{eff} L_{FIRMOS,eff}^{\downarrow} - \tau_{eff} E_{eff}^{\downarrow} - E^{\uparrow}}{\tau(B(T_s) - \tau_{eff} L_{FIRMOS,eff}^{\downarrow} - E_{eff}^{\downarrow})} \quad (24)$$

Figure 18 shows the spectral emissivity for the Spacecool sample. Unfortunately, the results for the 3M sample are not satisfactory. The large variance in the sample temperature may indicate an issue with temperature acquisition, possibly due to poor contact between the PT100 sensor and the sample surface.

3.5 Measurement technique at DFM

3.5.1 Design and measurement principle

The spectral emissivity of heated samples was directly measured using a modified two-temperature FTIR method developed at Risø [21]. This involved three spectra: the sample at the target temperature, at ambient temperature, and a blackbody reference at a chosen temperature. Sample temperature was monitored with a calibrated Pt-100 (~2 mm below the surface), and the blackbody with a calibrated Pt-100 resistance thermometer.

While DFM as a state-of-the-art Thermo Fischer iS50 FTIR spectrometer equipped with a dedicated directional emissivity setup, the measurements presented here were performed with an older but well-established FTIR spectrometer, Bomem model MB155, that has been in continuous use since the 1990s. This instrument has a long record of reliable performance and was chosen to ensure consistency with previous measurement campaigns, as well as for logistical reasons. A resolution of 8 cm^{-1} was used and measurement series with 200 and 800 scans were performed.

A reference blackbody with emissivity exceeding 0.995 was used. The temperature was measured with a calibrated sensor, with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The cavity temperature is uniform within approximately $\pm 0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 20: Sample holder placed on in-prompto setup. The off-axis gold mirrors coupling into the FTIR spectrometer are shown.

Figure 21: Bomen MB155 FTIR measuring reference blackbody at room temperature and 70 °C. An electrically heated blackbody as well as a blackbody with temperature-controlled water bath was used.

Measurements of directional emissivity

The subtraction method as described in [22] is used, with measurements of the emission from the sample surface at a given heightened setpoint (70°C), one at ambient temperature and a spectrum from a known high-emissivity blackbody. The ratio then yields the apparent emissivity.

3.5.2 Uncertainty budget estimation

The uncertainty in the spectral emissivity measurements is influenced by several factors: the FTIR spectrometer, the wavelength, the temperature uncertainty, the presence of absorbing gases (CO₂ and H₂O) in the optical path, the temperature of the sample and blackbody, and the emissivity of the sample. The measurements were carried out using an FTIR spectrometer equipped with a KBr beamsplitter with extended range and a DTGS detector at room temperature, covering the spectral range from approximately 450 to 8000 cm⁻¹. Both the blackbody reference and the sample were maintained at 70.0 °C, resulting in very weak thermal radiation above 2500 cm⁻¹. The uncertainty of the sample temperature, measured with a calibrated thermocouple, is estimated at 0.2 °C, while the uncertainty of the blackbody reference temperature, measured with a working normal (628-106), is 0.05 °C. The uncertainty is comparable across all samples, as the measurements were conducted at the same temperature, with similar emissivity levels, and under identical experimental conditions. Measurements were repeated over both short (minutes to hours) and long (months) time intervals. Drift was minimized by reducing the time between blackbody reference and sample measurements. The strong CO₂ absorption peak at 2350 cm⁻¹ is generally visible, although in principle it should be cancelled if CO₂ and H₂O concentrations and the optical path length remain constant between reference and sample measurements.

Figure 22: Uncertainty ($k=1$) on spectral emissivity measurements from 3 – 22 μm ($455 - 3333 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) with two major contributions, i.e. uncertainty found from ratio of two measurements (left) and uncertainty that equals 0.2°C uncertainty on the sample temperature (right) based on Planck’s law with a sample at 70°C in ambient (23°C).

Figure 23: Combined uncertainty ($k=1$) on spectral emissivity measurements from 3 – 22 μm . The uncertainty is similar for all 3 samples. The uncertainty below 5 μm can be lowered by raising the sample temperature, but it could have a temperature effect on the sample optical properties.

3.6 Measurement technique at FIW

3.6.1 Design and measurement principle

The TIR100-2 emissiometer is a commercial instrument allowing measurements of the total near-normal emissivity of opaque materials from very low to very high emissivity. It is manufactured and distributed by Inglas GmbH & Co.KG in Germany [23]. It measures the hemispherical near-normal reflectance of the test specimen. A high emissivity hemisphere heated at 100°C produces the radiation incident on the test specimen surface. A radiometric detection system, made from an infrared lens and a thermopile as a detector, is used to measure the radiation reflected by the test specimen in a direction of 12° relative to the surface's normal. The instrument is calibrated using a polished aluminium surface for lower emissivities (high reflectance) and a black corrugated surface for high emissivities (low reflectance). Between the two levels of emissivity used from calibration, the response of the instrument is assumed to be linear with reflectance or emissivity. The principle of measurement is described in [24], [25] and [26]. The wavelength spectrum ranges from 2.5 to 40 μm, with the maximum radiation energy at 8 μm. The device measures the reflected infrared radiation and uses this to calculate the emissivity (ϵ), which is represented as a dimensionless quantity in the range from 0 to 1 as a decimal number with three decimal places.

Figure 24: Measuring principle of the TIR 100-2 emissivity meter [23]

In order to achieve the highest possible measurement accuracy, the temperature of the black hemisphere must be as uniform as possible (stable over time) and as consistent as possible (across the inner surface of the hemisphere). This is usually achieved after a pre-heating time of one hour and ensured by the usage of the apparatus in a stable lab-environment with low temperature fluctuations and low air-speeds. Before starting the measurement series, a two-point calibration with the certified calibration standard is required. The calibration standard consists of two defined surfaces: a polished aluminium surface (low emissivity $\epsilon_{\text{low}} = 0.010$) and a textured black surface (high emissivity $\epsilon_{\text{high}} = 0.960$). The measurement procedure is based on the results and recommendations from the EMIRIM project [27]

3.6.2 Aging

The most important factor during outdoor weathering is UV radiation. Over the course of the year, the highest total radiation occurs in summer, and the high temperatures in summer are also expected to accelerate photochemical reactions. Since the temperature measured on the sample surface (microclimate), in addition to the radiation absorption of the surface, depends significantly on the spectral composition of the light source (sunlight vs. artificial light sources), the type of radiation source used can also be relevant to the ageing result.

Figure 25, left, shows the spectrum of a UV-A fluorescent lamp compared to the spectrum of a xenon arc lamp and the spectrum of sunlight. It is clear that the UV-A fluorescent lamp reproduces the UV-A and UV-B range relevant for damage to plastics. Due to the increased radiation in the long-wave infrared range of the

samples and the resulting radiation cooling effect, it is assumed for this ageing process that the samples do not heat up in sunlight and that the temperature of the samples do not differ significantly.

Figure 25 Left: Spectral distribution of a UV-A fluorescent lamp, xenon arc lamp and sunlight [28]; Right: Isolines of annual global radiation in GJ/m² [29].

The right graph of Figure 25 shows the isolines for different climate zones in Europe according to the annual global (solar) radiative energy. The isoline at 5 GJ/m² separates climate zones with high and moderate UV exposure and can therefore be regarded as a representative average value in Europe. According to [29], approximately 6% of total radiation falls within the ultraviolet range of wavelengths from 300 to 400 nm. A further reduction factor of 67% is applied to take into account that not all radiation occurs at high temperatures in summer. This results in an annual UV-A radiation of 5 GJ/(m²·a) x 0.06 x 0.67 = 0.201 GJ/(m²·a). These assumptions form the basis for the approximate estimate that UV weathering of 55 MJ/m² represents approximately 4 weeks of summer in Spain. Additional numbers for radiative energy and exposure time can be found in Table 11.

The weathering equipment used by FIW is made by the company Q-Lab and can simulate the combined effects of UV radiation, elevated temperatures and water condensation on the sample surface and/or water spray. During outdoor weathering, moisture can accumulate in the form of liquid water (rain) or condensation. While condensation usually represents a long-lasting moisture load over the course of the day, which may also penetrate deeper into the surface structure, rain represents short-term wetting, which can, however, lead to very rapid temperature changes (so-called thermal shocks) in summer, for example. Both cases can be relevant for the ageing of plastics.

Table 11: Duration of UV exposure in the Q-Lab ageing tester and corresponding radiative energy as well as an estimation of the corresponding summer time in Spain

Time	UV-A exposure		represents approximately:
t=0 (0 days)	0	MJ/m ²	MJ/m ²
t=1 (7 days)	27.5	MJ/m ²	2 weeks of summer in Spain
t=2 (14 days)	55.0	MJ/m ²	4 weeks of summer in Spain
t=3 (28 days)	110.0	MJ/m ²	8 weeks of summer in Spain
Total	192.5	MJ/m ²	14 weeks of summer in Spain

To test durability under UV exposure, two test specimens from each sample (3M Tape/3M R&D PRCF /SpaceCool/CoolingPhotonics VR98RF & VR98G4) were placed in a UV oven for ageing. A total of two ageing tests were carried out. The samples are not only exposed to UV radiation and elevated temperatures,

but also to condensation or water spray, depending on the ageing test. The UVA 340 UV lamps used are controlled at 0.83W/m^2 at 340nm to ensure constant radiation. The conditions in the ageing oven are shown in the Table 12 below.

Table 12: Ageing conditions of the two ageing tests carried out on the Parametric samples

Test condition according to DIN EN ISO 16474-3:2021 (Paints and varnishes)						
	Cycle	Exposure time	Type of lamp	Irradiance	Temperature of the blackboard	RH
No.		h		W/m ² /nm by 340 nm	°C	%
1	Dry	8	UVA-340	0.83	60	Not regulated
	Condensation	4	-	-	50	Not regulated
2	Dry	5	UVA-340	0.83	50	Not regulated
	Spray	1	-	-	20-30	Not regulated

In the first set of ageing conditions (test 1), the specimens were exposed to the mentioned artificial ageing conditions for a total of 7 weeks. The specimens were exposed to UV radiation and elevated temperature as well as a condensation cycle with a temperature range of 50-60°C according to table 11. After 1, 2 and 4 weeks, the emissivity of the specimens was determined using the TIR-100-2 measuring device.

In the second set of ageing conditions (test 2), a new set of specimens were exposed to ageing for a total of 7 weeks as well, but with different conditions. The specimens were exposed to UV radiation and elevated temperatures of 50-60°C as well but faced a spray cycle additionally, where water is sprayed onto the specimens for one hour to simulate rain incidents, according to table 12. After 1, 2 and 4 weeks, the emissivity and the weight of the specimens was determined using the TIR-100-2 measuring device.

Procedure for measuring the specimen

The test specimens are dried and left overnight in the laboratory to ensure that they are at the same temperature as the calibration standard. For the measurement, the test specimen is positioned in front of a black metal block to limit an increase of the temperature of the test specimen during the measurement (resulting from the heated half-sphere at 100°C). The metal block is kept at laboratory environment temperature and acts like a heat-sink on the backside of the test specimens. It enables thermal inertia during the test procedure. The test specimens are then placed in front of the device so that their position is plane against the device's spacers. Despite the heat-sink, the test specimen is exposed to heat from the heat emitting hemisphere, therefore the measurement time is kept as short as possible (≈ 3 s). The area tested on the test specimen has a diameter of approximately 5 mm (see sketch in Fig. 1 for details). Each test specimen is then measured four times, in different positions. All measuring points are located centrally on the sample within a diameter of approx. 30 mm. Four different test specimens are tested in turns to allow the materials to cool down again in order to reduce measurement errors from temperature increase of the samples as far as possible. Recalibration of the measurement apparatus is performed every 20 minutes to compensate for the thermal drift of the emitter. For all measurements, the temperature of the black body radiator is 100 °C, $\pm 0,5$ K, as recommended by the manufacturer. The test specimens are 100×100 mm, which is larger than the minimum requirement of 70×70 mm, allowing to cover the entire opening of the hemisphere completely.

Figure 26: Left: Demonstration image of the TIR100-2 device with the sample holder (black block) and the sample positioned in front of it (silver). Right: Example of the measurement process; the sample is pressed against the spacers of the TIR 100-2 using the sample holder

3.6.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

According to the manufacturer's specifications, the measuring range of the instrument is $\epsilon < 0.020 \dots 0.980$, with an accuracy in the range of ± 0.002 . The highest measured emissivity is 0.913, which is within the measuring range and calibration range. The lowest emissivity measured was 0.016, which is still within the calibration range but outside the measurement range specified by the manufacturer. A higher measurement error has to be assumed here, but as this result came from a "destroyed" sample, the practical relevance of this is small.

Each material is measured four times, and the mean value is then calculated from these results. The deviation between the minimum and maximum values averaged for all test specimens is 0.0034.

3.6.4 Results

Ageing condition set 1 (condesating moisture):

The resulting emissivities, separately displayed for two samples of five different materials are shown in Figure 27 for the first set of ageing conditions. The different symbols indicate the elapsed time of applied ageing conditions, from t_0 (test before the start of the ageing cycles), t_1 (after one week), t_2 (after two weeks) and t_3 (after four weeks) of applied ageing conditions.

The two separate samples of the "SpaceCool" PDRC material show no significant change in the emissivity in the long-wave infrared range during the ageing test. All four measurement points are very close to each other and lie within the measurement uncertainty.

Similar results can be found for the two samples of the "3M R&D PRCF" Material, that show no significant influence on emissivity from the applied ageing conditions and their duration as well. Same as for the "SpaceCool" Material can be found here, as all four measurement points are within the measurement uncertainty range of the TIR-100 machine.

The two samples of the "3M tape" show an increase in the emissivity from before the ageing cycles (starting at 0.62 and 0.65) to 0.67 and 0.69 after one week, further increasing to 0.74 after two weeks, before a huge decrease of the emissivity can be detected for step 3 (after four weeks). This huge decrease comes from the destruction of the samples during the last aging step, resulting in a measurement of the emissivity of the aluminum sample carrier and therefore showing a very high reflection in the IR-range.

The "V98RF" samples also show an increase in emissivity from t_0 to t_1 . The first sample then shows very low emissivity after t_2 , resulting from destruction (complete peeling of layers could be observed). The second sample shows the same flaking, but only after the third aging step (after four weeks). The very low emissivities in the IR-range come from the highly reflective aluminum substrate, that is dominating the measurement after the destruction of the samples.

Both samples of the material “V89TG4” show an increase from the initial values (0.63) to 0.70 and 0.71 after t1. The results then stay around these values (within the measurement uncertainty of the TIR-100) also after t2 and t3, showing no further influence of the ageing conditions.

Figure 27: Results of emissivity change of two samples of the five tested PDRC materials during ageing under UV radiation and condensation. The measured values are indicated as t0 (before ageing), after one week (t1), two weeks (t2) and four weeks (t3).

Ageing condition set 2 (water spray test):

The results of the emissivity measurements on two samples of each of the five different PDRC materials after applying the second set of ageing conditions (water spray exposure) are shown in Figure 28. The different symbols indicate the elapsed time of applied ageing conditions, from t0 (test before the start of the ageing cycles), t1 (after one week), t2 (after two weeks) and t3 (after four weeks) of applied ageing conditions.

The two separate samples of the “SpaceCool” PDRC material show no significant change in the emissivity in the long-wave infrared range during the ageing test. Initial readings show 0.81 for both samples. The results stay at very similar values throughout the ageing procedure (in between 0.81 and 0.82) and all results lie within the measurement uncertainty range of the TIR-100.

Similar results can be found for the two samples of the “3M R&D PRCF” Material, that show no significant influence on emissivity from the applied ageing conditions as well. All results for both samples and all ageing steps are within 0.82 and 0.83 and therefore lie within the measurement uncertainty range of the TIR-100 machine.

The emissivity of the “3m tape” samples is 0.67 (sample 1) and 0.68 (sample 2) for the initial measurement and remains at these values after one week of ageing. Both samples then show an increase in the emissivity readings from t1 to t2 (0.71 and 0.72). This increases further after another two weeks of ageing (at t3) to 0.79.

The “V98RF” samples have an initial emissivity of 0.65. A slight increase can be found at t1 (0.70 and 0.71). Sample 1 then shows a further increase to 0.75 at t2 before the values drop significantly for t3, resulting from the destruction of the material. Sample 2 shows that significant drop already after the ageing of step t2 and the ageing at t3 is not continued.

The two samples of the material “V89TG4” show an initial emissivity reading of 0.71 and 0.72, which does not change at all during the ageing procedure. All further readings are not significant and lie within the measurement uncertainty range of the TIR 100 machine.

Figure 28: Results of emissivity change of two samples of the five tested PDRC materials during ageing under UV radiation and spray water. The measured values are indicated as t0 (before ageing), after one week (t1), two weeks (t2) and four weeks (t3).

In addition to emissivity, the mass change of the samples was also recorded during the ageing tests with UV radiation and spray water (see diagram 29). The weight of the samples was measured including the aluminum substrate. Both “SpaceCool” samples show a slight increase in mass, which is probably due to deposits during the first steps, before a loss of mass is observed in the final ageing step, indicating possible material degradation.

Both samples of “3M R&D PRCF” show almost no change of their mass at all across all ageing stages.

For both samples of “3M tape”, a minimal increase in mass is noticeable at the beginning, which turns into a significant loss of mass during further ageing and the material is destroyed.

The “V98RF” samples initially show a slight increase in mass, followed by a high loss of mass after as a result of destruction of the sample. The second sample “V98RF” is already defective after the first ageing step and shows a loss of mass that slightly increases further during the third step, possibly due to washing away of the adhesive. Sample “V98G4”, on the other hand, shows no relevant change in mass during the entire ageing test.

Figure 29: Mass change of the samples during ageing under UV radiation and spray water. The measured values in percent relative to initial weight after one week (t1), two weeks (t2) and four weeks (t3) are shown.

3.7 Measurement techniques at Aalto

3.7.1 Design and measurement principle

Measurements were carried out at the facilities in Metrology Research Institute at Aalto University. The measurements are performed using three complementary instruments including Aalto's reference gonireflectometer, 3D gonireflectometer, and Cary 7000 spectrophotometer equipped with diffuse reflectance accessory.

Reference gonio-reflectometer

The reference setup is an absolute gonireflectometer (Figure 30) composed of a broadband, monochromated source and a multi-arm detection system that lets you control both illumination and viewing geometry. Illumination comes from a 50 W quartz tungsten–halogen lamp and a 450 W xenon arc lamp coupled into a double monochromator covering $\sim 300\text{--}1700\text{ nm}$; a grating change near 950 nm selects UV–Vis or NIR, and the output bandwidth is set to $\sim 5\text{ nm}$ (Vis) or $\sim 14\text{ nm}$ (NIR). The beam is steered by mirrors, passes a polarizer and iris (setting the spot to $\sim 12\text{ mm}$ in the Vis and $\sim 8\text{ mm}$ in the NIR), and a small split to a monitor photodiode (Si for $300\text{--}950\text{ nm}$, Ge for $950\text{--}1700\text{ nm}$) corrects source drift. The sample sits on a turntable that sets the incident angle, while a heavy-duty detector arm sets the viewing angle to scan the BRDF/diffuse response. Collected light passes through a baffled aperture and a plano-convex collection lens ($f \approx 100\text{ mm}$) that focuses onto an under-filled detector at the focal plane. With an average sample-to-aperture distance of $\sim 472.9\text{ mm}$, the detection solid angle is $\sim 0.0022\text{ sr}$ (full angular width $\approx 3.03^\circ$), providing well-defined angular resolution for accurate diffuse reflectance measurements. [30]

Figure 30: Schematic of Aalto's reference gonireflectometer.

3D gonio-reflectometer

The 3D gonireflectometer (Figure 31) is a fiber-coupled, laser-illuminated BRDF instrument that measures scattered radiant flux with full control of in- and out-of-plane geometries. A three-axis goniometer sets the illumination zenith, while two orthogonal detector arms set the viewing azimuth and zenith; the sample stage can also rotate to vary the incident azimuth. An optical rail conditions the beam with a collimator, iris, order-sorting filters, and a beam splitter to a monitor detector. Illumination is delivered from a supercontinuum laser

and spectrally selected by a laser-line tunable filter (LLTF), providing broadband, high-power light (≈ 300 mW in the visible, ~ 2 mW/nm power density) that can be narrowed without moving parts. Scattered light is routed via fibers beneath the stage to interchangeable detectors (Si, InGaAs, and extended InGaAs), while the horizontal sample holder accommodates different shapes and thicknesses by swapping holder types and adjusting height. This configuration enables precise, out-of-plane 3D BRDF/diffuse-reflectance measurements across the visible–NIR. [31]

The measurement from this device is relative to the one measured from the reference gonioreflectometer.

Figure 31: 3D gonioreflectometer. (1) illumination system, (2) monitor detector, (3) illumination angle rotatory stage, (4) viewing azimuthal angle rotatory stage, (5) viewing zenith angle rotatory stage, (6) collection parabolic off-axis mirror, (7) horizontal sample holder.

Cary 7000 UV-Vis-NIR Spectrophotometer

The spectral and total hemispherical solar reflectance of the samples was measured with an Agilent Cary 7000 UV-Vis-NIR double-beam spectrophotometer (Figure 32), equipped with a 150 mm integrating sphere, covering the 0.35–2.3 μm wavelength range. This setup collects both specular and diffuse components at near-normal incidence, allowing precise determination of hemispherical optical properties. Before each measurement session, the instrument was calibrated using a certified PTFE (Spectralon®) reference plate (Labsphere) as the 100% reflectance standard, while a black trap was placed at the integrating sphere entrance to establish the 0% baseline by completely blocking the incident beam. For each sample, multiple scans were performed under controlled indoor conditions, and the mean values were reported to ensure measurement repeatability.

Figure 32: Schematic of Cary 7000 with diffuse reflectance accessory.

Example of measurement results

Figure 33 illustrates the results obtained with the Cary 7000 for the SpaceCool, 3M R&D PRCF, and Cooling Photonics samples. The results of measurements are traceable to scale of BRDF maintained by absolute reference gonireflectometer and via calibrated working standards.

Figure 33: Examples spectral diffuse reflectance of investigated materials in the project.

3.7.2 Uncertainty budget estimation

The characterization of the absolute instrument for its uncertainty parameters in directional-hemispherical reflectance (DHR) has been performed according to the GUM and has been reported earlier in [30] for the visible wavelength range and in [32] for the near-infrared wavelength range. Several of the uncertainty parameters in DHR can be applied to BRDF as well, such as the standard uncertainty in wavelength, solid angle, and detector linearity.

Table 13: List of the standard uncertainty components of the absolute instrument and their effect on the relative uncertainty in BRDF measurements. (VIS: 450 nm to 900 nm, NIR: 950 nm to 1650 nm, VZA = -35° to 35°)

Source of uncertainty Absolute Instrument	Standard uncertainty		Uncertainty in BRDF/ %	
	VIS	NIR	VIS	NIR
Measurement noise ^{a,b)}	0.27%	0.08%	0.27	0.08
Instrument reproducibility	0.10%	0.04%	0.10	0.04
Wavelength ^{c)}	0.1 nm	0.2 nm	<0.01	<0.01
Straylight (isochromatic)	0.14%	0.16%	0.14	0.16
Straylight (heterochromatic)	<0.01 %	<0.01 %	<0.01	<0.01
Near-infrared field-stop correction	-	0.14 %	-	0.14
Detector linearity ^{b)}	0.04%	0.09 %	0.04	0.09
Spatial nonuniformity ^{c)}	0.10%	0.06%	0.10	0.06
Solid angle (due to sample-detector distance)	0.15 mm	0.15 mm	0.06	0.06
Solid angle (due to detector aperture diameter)	2 μm	2 μm	0.02	0.02
Solid angle (due to sample surface level) ^{c)}	0.3 mm	0.3 mm	0.13	0.13
Illumination and viewing angles ^{a,c)}	0.10°	0.10°	<0.01-0.17	<0.01-0.17
Polarization ^{c)}	0.05 %	0.05%	0.05	0.05
Combined standard uncertainty			0.37-0.40	0.30-0.34
a) This uncertainty depends on the viewing zenith angle. b) This uncertainty depends on the detector type and selected gain of amplifiers. c) This uncertainty depends on the sample.				

3.8 Measurement techniques at TUBITAK

3.8.1 Design and measurement principle

In TUBITAK the spectral diffuse reflectance measurements are carried out using a Cary 7000 double beam spectrometer equipped with a 150 mm integrating sphere at 8°/d geometry (Figure 34). In this system, the measurements can be performed in the wavelength range from 250 nm to 2500 nm either including (8°: di) or excluding (8°: de) specular component of the reflectance. In diffuse reflectance measurements as a reference standard spectralon coated, diffuse reflectance standard is used. The traceability of this reference standard is done in two ways. First, it is calibrated in PTB and then checked with the BRDF system established in TUBITAK. The measurement accuracy of the BRDF system was ensured through comparisons made within the scope of the 20SCP01 Smart PhoRa project.

Figure 34: Diffuse reflectance measurement system

In this work totally four PRC materials are used. These materials are V98 Almeco substrate coated with Spacecool made PRC film (V98 + Space Cool), V98 Almeco substrate coated with 3M Tape type PRC (V98 + 3M Tape), V98TG4 Cooling Photonic Substrate coated with Cooling Photonic PRC film (V98TG4 + CP) and 3M R&D PRCF substrate coated with 3M white foil PRC (3M R&D PRCF + 3M).

The diffuse reflectance measurements were done in the following order. First, reference diffuse reflectance standard was placed to the sample holder of integrating sphere and baseline measurements with zero line correction (Baseline - Zeroline) were done. Then, reference diffuse reflectance standard was removed from the sample holder and the PRC materials were placed to the sample holder and measurements with zero line corrections (Sample - Zeroline) were performed. After we complete measurements the diffuse reflectance values of PRC materials were calculated using the following equation

$$\rho_{PRC}(\lambda) = \left[\frac{Sample(\lambda) - Zeroline(\lambda)}{Baseline(\lambda) - Zeroline(\lambda)} \right] \rho_{ref}(\lambda)$$

Where ρ_{PRC} and ρ_{ref} are reflectance values of PRC and reference standard respectively.

Since the PRC materials studied in this work package were also used in the work package for the ageing test, the diffuse reflectance measurements were done before and after each ageing test. The measurement results obtained for totally four PRC samples are given in the following figures.

Figure 35: Diffuse reflectance measurement results of PRC samples

In order to distinguish whether the changes in the reflectance data obtained before and after each aging process were due to aging or to the instability of the samples over time (approximately four months), before the aging tests the stability of all samples was tested. Results are given in Figure 36. For each PRC sample, the stability levels were determined by comparing the changes in the measurements taken at four different times with the uncertainty of the reference standard. As can be seen in Figure 36, the changes in all samples are less than 1 %. Therefore, if the changes in reflectance values after aging tests were greater than this value, this change was considered to be due to aging.

In this context, when the changes calculated from the data in Figure 37, it is seen that for V98 + 3M Tape V98TG4 + CP and 3M R&D PRCF + 3M samples the changes in the wavelength between 500 nm and 2500 nm are less than 1%, but the changes below 500 nm wavelength, especially in the UV region, are in the range of 2 %- 20%. Therefore, it can be considered that V98 + 3M Tape V98TG4 + CP and 3M R&D PRCF + 3M samples are resistant to three-cycle thermal cycling, humidity-freeze, damp heat and UV ageing in VIS and NIR regions, but less resistant in the UV region. When the changes in Figure 37 related to the V98 + Space Cool sample are examined, it is seen that this sample has weak resistance to three-cycle thermal cycling, humidity-freeze, damp heat and UV ageing.

Figure 36: Stability measurement results of PRC samples

Figure 37: Changes in the diffuse reflectance measurement results of PRC samples due to aging tests

3.9 Measurement techniques at IO-CSIC

3.9.1 Design and measurement

The measurement principle is the comparison of samples to a reference standard calibrated against the diffuse reflectance scale of the IO-CSIC. The comparison is done on a PERKIN-ELMER Lambda 1050 double-grating spectrophotometer fitted with a 60 mm diameter integrating sphere. The spectral range covered is 250 nm to 2500 nm.

The reference standard for calibration is made on spectralon, calibrated by PTB in 2025. Measurements were done every 5 nm with a fixed bandwidth of 5 nm in the (250-860) nm range and a variable bandwidth (below 20 nm) in the interval (860-2500) nm.

Room temperature was in the range $(23 \pm 1) ^\circ\text{C}$.

Spot size on the samples to be characterized is 11 x 2 mm, as measured for a white spot.

Reflectance is calculated according to the formula

$$\rho_m(\lambda) = \left\{ \frac{S_m(\lambda) + \delta_{rm} + \delta_\lambda - S_0(\lambda)}{S_{100}(\lambda) - S_0(\lambda)} \rho_p(\lambda) + K_i(\lambda) \left[\beta \frac{S_m(\lambda) + \delta_{rm} + \delta_\lambda - S_0(\lambda)}{S_{100}(\lambda) - S_0(\lambda)} - \alpha \right] \right\} f(\rho_{sc})$$

Where the meaning of the variables is

Table 14

Symbol	Meaning
S_m	Spectrophotometer Reading for the sample to be measured
δ_{rm}	Correction due to resolution
δ_λ	Correction due to wavelength
S_0	Spectrophotometer Reading for a null reflectance device
S_{100}	Spectrophotometer Reading for the reference standard
ρ_p	Reflectance of the standard
K_i	Correction for specular component due to incorrect measurement of specular component on the sphere
f	Spectrophotometer calibration factor (primarily due to the linearity)
α	Constant whose value is 1 if the sample is glossy and 0 if it is matt.
β	Constant whose value is 1 if the reference standard is glossy and 0 if it is matt.

The PRC materials characterized in spectral reflectance are V98RF from Almecco+CP, SpaceCool White and 3M R&D PRCF. The following figure shows an scheme of the experimental setup and examples of spectral reflectance curves obtained in the solar spectral range for those materials

Figure 38: Measurement setup and reflectance spectra of three PRC materials obtained at the IO.

3.9.2 Uncertainty budget estimation

Expanded relative uncertainty ($k=2$) on the spectral reflectance depends on wavelength as shown in the following table, where the distribution of spectral intervals is determined by the uncertainty of the reflectance standard used:

Table 15

Wavelength / nm	Relative standard uncertainty
[250, 400]	2 %
(400, 1850]	1 %
(1850, 2200]	1,5 %
(2200, 2400]	2,5 %
(2440, 2500]	3 %

The main contributions to uncertainty come from the uncertainty of the standard and the specular component correction.

3.10 Measurement techniques at IETcc-CSIC

3.10.1 Design and measurement principle

The solar reflectance data at IETcc-CSIC was collected using a portable fiber-optic setup designed for both laboratory and field measurements. The system consists of a high-power tungsten halogen light source and a PTFE-coated integrating sphere (both from Ocean Optics), coupled by an 800 μm optical fiber. The sphere has a diameter of 50 mm and an 8 mm sample port. The incident beam forms an angle of 8° with the normal to the sample surface, and a gloss trap allows for exclusion of the specular component. A bifurcated fiber links the sphere to two StellarNet spectrometers (Fig. 39) that cover the VIS–NIR range: the Black Comet spectrometer measures from 380 to 1080 nm, and the Dwarf Star spectrometer from 900 to 1700 nm. A 5 cm diameter Spectralon disk is used as the reflectance standard, with traceability to U.S. national measurement standards through a Labsphere certificate.

Figure 39: Portable reflectance measurement setup and mean reflectance spectra of three PRC materials obtained at the IETcc.

The experimental procedure is as follows: first, the light source is blocked to establish the 0% baseline; second, the Spectralon panel is used as the high-reflectance standard to define the 100% reference on the spectrometers. Then, the integrating sphere is placed on the samples to collect their reflectance spectra at different locations, from which an average spectrum is obtained (ρ_{sample}).

Two corrections are applied to the raw data. First, a dark-signal correction, derived from measurements with a light trap placed at the sample port, accounts for radiation losses due to the setup geometry (Zero) and yields a more realistic signal. Second, a correction based on the certified reflectance spectrum of the Spectralon standard (ρ_{ref}) compensates for the fact that its actual curve lies slightly below 100%. With these corrections the reflectance is calculated with equation $\rho_{\text{PRC}} = \rho_{\text{ref}} (\rho_{\text{sample}} - \text{Zero}) / (100 - \text{Zero})$.

The mean reflectance spectra of the three PRC benchmark materials of the Parametric project are collected in Figure 39.

The emissivity measurements were performed with a portable Surface Optics ET100 emissometer shown in Figure 40. The ET100 measures in six spectral bands: 1.5–2.0 μm , 2.0–3.5 μm , 3.0–4.0 μm , 4.0–5.0 μm , 5.0–10.5 μm and 10.5–21.0 μm . The instrument head is a gold-coated integrating sphere that acquires directional-hemispherical reflectance in those bands at two incident beam angles (20° and 60°). The ET100 uses six detector elements to cover the stated bands: two PbSe and two PbS elements housed in a single thermoelectrically cooled package (each with its bandpass filter), plus two DLATGS detectors. These detector/filter combinations ensure each element only senses its intended spectral band.

Figure 40: ET100 portable emissometer from Surface Optics Corporation. Left - general view of the equipment; centre - front view of the sample port; right - placement of the device on the sample surface.

A gold calibration coupon was used to calibrate the emissometer prior to the measurements. Then, the integrating-sphere head is pressed directly against the surface under test; a rubber ring protects the sample and provides a non-slip seal. The round opening at the end of the sphere serves as the IR illumination port and the entry for light scattered and/or reflected by the sample. During a measurement, the IR beam is internally rotated through its measurement positions so the sample is illuminated at 20° and 60° and the sample reflectance is measured in each band and geometry. After each measurement, the sample is removed from the port in order to record a zero reflectance measurement.

Six different samples were analyzed with the emissometer: two samples of the 3M R&D PRCF material, three samples of Spacecool silvery material and one sample of the V98RF system. For each sample, measurements were recorded at different locations and used to compute the two mean directional emissivities. The emissometer then calculates the total hemispherical emissivity from the directional data at 20°, assuming the sample is completely opaque and dielectric or metallic according to the option selected by the operator. Figure 41 collects the reflectance measured at 20° in the different wavelength intervals for the six samples, while Figure 42 shows the numerical values provided by the equipment for the directional total emissivity at the two measuring angles (DTE20 and DTE60) and the hemispherical total emissivity (HTE).

Figure 41: Reflectance measured at 20° of incidence for six samples of PRC materials in different wavelength intervals within the thermal infrared range.

Figure 42: Directional total emittance (DTE) at 20° and 60° of incidence and hemispherical total emittance (HTE) provided by the ET100 emissometer for six samples of PRC material.

3.10.2 Uncertainty budget estimation

The uncertainty budget is kept focused on the main contributors. The terms considered are the standard uncertainty of the readings (ρ_{sample} , 100 and Zero in equation (1)), the Spectralon reference uncertainty, and the sample heterogeneity that is taken as the standard deviation of the measurements in different positions of the surface. The Spectralon certificate uncertainty is shown in Table 16 and is considered the main contributor to the uncertainty.

Table 16: Uncertainty of the reflectance spectra of the Spectralon reference.

CALIBRATION AND MEASUREMENT CAPABILITIES (CMC)			
Measured Parameter or Device Calibrated	Range	Uncertainty ($k=2$)	Remarks
OPTICAL RADIATION			
Photometric (20/O02)			
Relative Reflectance at Wavelength Shown Below: 250 nm to 600 nm	up to 0.02	0.0016	Relative reflectance is a dimensionless quantity
	> 0.02 to 0.05	0.0029	
	> 0.05 to 0.10	0.012	
	> 0.10 to 0.20	0.012	
	> 0.20 to 0.50	0.0054	
	> 0.50 to 0.80	0.0054	
	> 0.80 to 0.99	0.0053	
601 nm to 1500 nm	up to 0.02	0.0017	
	> 0.02 to 0.05	0.0022	
	> 0.05 to 0.10	0.0025	
	> 0.10 to 0.20	0.0052	
	> 0.20 to 0.50	0.0064	
	> 0.50 to 0.80	0.0064	
	> 0.80 to 0.99	0.0049	
1501 nm to 2200 nm	up to 0.02	0.0090	
	> 0.02 to 0.05	0.0090	
	> 0.05 to 0.10	0.015	
	> 0.10 to 0.20	0.015	
	> 0.20 to 0.50	0.0099	
	> 0.50 to 0.80	0.0083	
	> 0.80 to 0.99	0.0088	
2201 nm to 2500 nm	up to 0.02	0.054	
	> 0.02 to 0.05	0.054	
	> 0.05 to 0.10	0.043	
	> 0.10 to 0.20	0.043	
	> 0.20 to 0.50	0.035	
	> 0.50 to 0.80	0.028	
	> 0.80 to 0.99	0.032	
END			

The emissivity measurements were performed with the Surface Optics ET100 and, because all runs were carried out inside the 0–40 °C temperature window, the ET100’s reflectance accuracy quoted at 20° (± 0.03 reflectance units) are used as an accuracy term. The instrument’s nominal angular tolerance ($\pm 1^\circ$ at the 20° and 60° positions) was also taken into account, since small deviations in incidence angle affect the directional readings and therefore the hemispherical emissivity. Finally, each sample was measured in different locations and the standard deviation across those measurements was taken as the sampling variability term in the uncertainty budget.

3.11 Measurement techniques at NKUA

3.11.1 Design and measurement principle

All measurements were carried out at the facilities of the GRBES – Building Environmental Research Group of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA). GRBES is a research unit with long-standing expertise in the experimental thermal and optical characterization of construction and urban materials, certified under ISO 9001 and operating in line with international standards and best laboratory practices. The laboratory is fully equipped with state-of-the-art instrumentation for the assessment of both hemispherical spectral reflectance and directional-hemispherical emissivity of surfaces. For the purposes of this study, two complementary instruments were employed: the AE1-RD portable emissometer and the Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer with a 150 mm integrating sphere. Routine maintenance of the instruments is performed at regular intervals according to the manufacturers' specifications, ensuring their long-term reliability. Both instruments are periodically subjected to internal quality control checks (e.g., calibration, repeatability and consistency tests) and participate in interlaboratory proficiency schemes to validate measurement comparability. In particular, the Cary 5000 spectrophotometer is more frequently involved in Collaborative Testing Services (CTS, USA) interlaboratory proficiency schemes for reflectance, following relevant ASTM/ISO standards.

AE1-RD Portable Emissometer

The hemispherical thermal emissivity of the samples in the infrared range (near room temperature) was determined using a Devices & Services AE1 emissometer coupled with the RD1 scaling voltmeter, following ASTM C1371-04a. The instrument measures the infrared radiation emitted from the sample surface and compares it with manufacturer-supplied reference standards. Calibration was performed before each measurement session using two certified reference plates: a low-emissivity standard ($\varepsilon = 0.05$, nickel-plated brass, DSC33) and a high-emissivity standard ($\varepsilon = 0.89$, hard black anodised aluminum with PTFE, DSC23), both supplied with an ISO calibration certificate and a stated uncertainty of ± 0.02 . Linearity of the instrument scale between the two anchors was verified using an intermediate reference plate (DSC53, $\varepsilon = 0.559 \pm 0.002$). Measurements were conducted under controlled indoor conditions, with the probe placed in direct contact with the sample surface to minimize external radiation interference. For each sample, multiple readings were taken to evaluate repeatability, and the mean value was reported.

Regarding traceability, it is noted that no official Standard Reference Material (SRM) exists for low-temperature hemispherical emittance; instead, Devices & Services maintains its own factory reference set and provides the sole calibration basis. In line with the manufacturer's recommendations, NKUA operates with a working set of emissivity standards complemented by a reserved reference set, which is used periodically to verify the accuracy and stability of the working set.

Figure 43: Devices & Services AE1 emissometer with RD1 used at NKUA for total hemispherical emittance.

Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR Spectrophotometer

Spectral and total hemispherical solar reflectance of the samples was measured using an Agilent Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR double-beam spectrophotometer equipped with a 150 mm integrating sphere (Labsphere, DRA-2500), covering the 0.25–2.5 μm range. This configuration collects both specular and diffuse components at near-normal incidence, enabling accurate determination of hemispherical optical properties. The measurements were conducted in accordance with ASTM E903-12 and ASTM G159-98 standards.

Prior to each measurement session, the instrument was calibrated using a certified PTFE (Spectralon®) reference plate (Labsphere) as the 100% reflectance standard, while a black trap was placed at the entrance of the integrating sphere to define the 0% baseline by fully blocking the incident beam. Measurements were performed in a temperature-controlled laboratory (25 ± 1 °C, 45 ± 5 % RH), using cleaned, substrate-free tiles of 7×7 cm (up to 10×10 cm maximum). Multiple scans were acquired for each sample under controlled indoor conditions, and the mean values were reported to account for repeatability.

Figure 44: Agilent Cary 5000 with 150 mm integrating sphere (DRA-2500) used at NKUA for hemispherical spectral reflectance (0.25–2.5 μm).

3.11.2 Uncertainty budget estimation

The uncertainty evaluation of the optical property measurements was carried out according to the ISO/IEC Guide 98-3 (GUM), in combination with relevant ASTM and ISO standards (ASTM C1371, ASTM E903). Both Type A (statistical, repeatability) and Type B (systematic, calibration and environmental) contributions were considered, combined as the root-sum-square of standard uncertainties, and expanded using a coverage factor $k = 2$ ($\approx 95\%$ confidence level).

For the AE1-RD emissometer, the main contributions were the calibration uncertainty of the supplied low- and high-emissivity standards ($\epsilon = 0.05$, $\epsilon = 0.89$, ± 0.02), instrument resolution and repeatability, and ambient laboratory stability. Repeated measurements yielded standard deviations below ± 0.005 , while scale linearity was verified using an intermediate reference plate. The expanded uncertainty for total hemispherical emissivity is estimated at ± 0.02 (absolute, $k = 2$).

For the Cary 5000 spectrophotometer, the budget included the calibration uncertainty of the PTFE (Spectralon®) 100 % reference and the black-trap zero, instrument photometric accuracy and baseline stability, wavelength accuracy (± 0.1 nm), and port alignment repeatability. Multiple scans per sample showed standard deviations below $\pm 0.3\%$ reflectance. Spectral uncertainties were propagated through the AM1.5 spectrum integration to obtain solar-weighted reflectance. External validation through CTS (USA) interlaboratory proficiency testing confirmed consistency within $\pm 1.2\%$ of the reference mean. The expanded uncertainty for solar-weighted reflectance is estimated at $\pm 1.5\%$ (relative, $k = 2$).

Both instruments operate within NKUA's ISO 9001 quality system, are regularly maintained and calibrated according to manufacturer specifications, and are supported by internal repeatability checks and external proficiency testing. The reported uncertainty values are therefore traceable, reproducible, and aligned with international best practice.

Table 17: Summary of uncertainty budget for emissivity and solar reflectance measurements ($k = 2$, $\approx 95\%$ C.L.)

Instrument / Parameter	Main Sources of Uncertainty (examples)	Type A (repeatability)	Type B (calibration, system)	Expanded Uncertainty (U)
AE1-RD Emissometer (Total hemispherical emissivity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calibration standards ($\epsilon = 0.05$, $\epsilon = 0.88$, ± 0.02) - Linearity check with intermediate plate - Instrument resolution & contact stability - Ambient laboratory drift 	$\sigma \leq \pm 0.005$	± 0.02 from calibration standards, manufacturer specs	± 0.02 (absolute)
Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR (Solar-weighted reflectance)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repeat scans per sample ($\sigma \leq \pm 0.3\%$) - Spectral noise during integration 	$\pm 0.3\%$ reflectance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spectralon® 100 % standard (± 1.0–1.5%) - Black trap zero ($\pm 0.3\%$) - Photometric linearity & wavelength accuracy (± 0.1 nm) - Sphere/port alignment 	$\pm 1.5\%$ (relative)

4 Comparative analysis in the MIR range

Before beginning the comparison, it should be noted that all measurements in Section 4 were performed on three selected benchmark materials SPACECOOL, V98RF and 3M R&D PRCF Foil, but the individual samples were manufactured for each partner according to the required geometry and size.

4.1 3M R&D PRCF Foil

Figure 45: Directional spectral emissivities of the 3M R&D PRCF Foil from 2.5 μm to 50 μm and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, LNE, CNR, PTB and DFM. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Figure 46: Directional spectral emissivities of the 3M R&D PRCF Foil: enlarged view of the Fig. 45, from 6.7 μm to 50 μm measured by partners: CAE, LNE, CNR, PTB and DFM. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Figure 47: Hemispherical emissivities of the 3M R&D PRCF Foil measured by partners: LNE, NKUA, FIW, PTB, RISE and CAE. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Figure 48: Directional total emissivities of the 3M R&D PRCF Foil measured by partners: PTB, IETccCSIC and CAE for the two angles of observation of 0/20° and 60° and for three wavelength ranges of 4 - 5 μm, 5 – 10.5 μm and 10.5 – 21 μm. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Overview of Emissivity Results

Comparative measurements of directional spectral emissivity of the 3M R&D PRCF Foil conducted by several partners generally show good agreement within the stated uncertainty ranges (Figures 45-46), with a few notable exceptions. In particular, discrepancies are observed between the measurements in the short-wavelength infrared region (2.5–5 μm).

These discrepancies are not reflected in the hemispherical emissivity data, where results from all partners LNE, NKUA, FIW, PTB, RISE align closely (Figure 47).

In addition, the results of the directional total emissivities show good agreement- within the measured uncertainty- among the partner laboratories (PTB, IETcc-CSIC, and CAE) for both observation angles (0/20° and 60°) and across the three wavelength ranges: 4–5 μm, 5–10.5 μm, and 10.5–21 μm.

CNR was unable to perform the planned open-air measurements due to unfavorable environmental conditions, resulting in an incomplete dataset for this analysis.

Discussion of Measurement Uncertainties

Several factors contribute to uncertainty in the directional emissivity comparison. For example, the differences in measurement geometry can be particularly relevant: CAE measures at an angle of 8°, PTB at 10°, and CNR at normal incidence (0°). While these angular differences can influence directional measurements, they are relatively small and unlikely to fully account for the observed discrepancies for the non-transparent materials (Figure 45).

Another potential source of variability is the use of thermal paste during the 3M foil mounting to the aluminium substrate, which may be applied inconsistently. As mentioned above, each partner had their own individual sample.

Surface contamination and material aging are also possible contributors to measurement differences (Figure 49): the figure shows what happened to the 3M sample when heated to 80 °C.

As previously noted, a significant deviation is observed between LNE, CAE, and PTB in the 2–5 μm region. PTB's measurements in this range were conducted using an integrating sphere rather than their standard emissivity reference setup, potentially introducing additional uncertainty: estimated at approximately 2.7% ($k = 1$).

In LNE's case, several factors have been assessed. Their setup is not particularly sensitive to surface contaminants or to the thermal grease between foil and substrate, and the consistency between two independent measurement spheres supports the reliability of their data. However, potential aging of the sample or slight differences between material batches may explain part of the deviation observed.

Figure 49: 3M R&D PRCF Foil after heating up to 80 °C: showing an ageing of this material

4.2 SPACECOOL

Figure 50: Directional spectral emissivities of the SPACECOOL sample from 2.5 μm to 50 μm and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, LNE, CNR, PTB and DFM. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Figure 51: Directional spectral emissivities of the SPACECOOL sample: enlarged view of the Fig. 50, from 6.7 μm to 50 μm measured by partners: CAE, LNE, CNR, PTB and DFM. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Figure 52: Hemispherical emissivities of the SPACECOOL sample: measured by partners: LNE, NKUA, FIW, PTB, RISE and CAE. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Figure 53: Directional total emissivities of the SPACECOOL sample measured by partners: PTB, IETccCSIC and CAE for the two angles of observation of 0/20° and 60° and for three wavelength ranges of 4 - 5 μm, 5 – 10.5 μm and 10.5 – 21 μm. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Overview of Emissivity Results

Overall, the directional spectral emissivity measurements of the SPACECOOL sample show good consistency among the different laboratories, particularly in the short-wavelength infrared range (2.5–5 μm). However, some discrepancies begin to appear at higher wavelengths, especially in the far-infrared region starting at 20 μm (Figure 51).

A notable observation is that PTB's hemispherical emissivity values appear higher than those of other institutes (Figure 52). This may be attributed to the difference in spectral integration ranges. PTB's hemispherical measurements were integrated in the 7–13 μm range, whereas RISE integrates over 2–25 μm, and LNE and FIW over an even broader range (2.5–40 μm). The broader integration naturally results in lower averaged values due to the inclusion of lower-emissivity regions at longer and shorter wavelengths.

In addition, the directional total emissivity results show good agreement - within the measured uncertainty - among the partner laboratories (PTB, IETcc-CSIC, and CAE) for both observation angles (0/20° and 60°) and across the three wavelength ranges: 4–5 μm, 5–10.5 μm, and 10.5–21 μm (Figure 53).

Discussion of Specific Data Features

DFM's data between 3 and 4 μm falls near the edge of their measurement range and contains significant noise; these values can be disregarded for comparative purposes.

CNR's open-air measurements exhibit a higher level of noise compared to laboratory measurements. Several factors may contribute to this: A relatively large distance (~1 meter) between the sample and detector; A measurement angle of 13.5°, rather than normal incidence; Long measurement durations (about 2 hours) with 24 individual spectra averaged.

External environmental influences, as the measurements were taken between 3–5 p.m. in January. While ambient temperature fluctuations were accounted for using hourly weather station data, some residual drift may still affect the results.

More specific discrepancies include the 6–7.5 μm range, where CNR’s open-air data shows unexpectedly high emissivity values. Since this lies near the upper limit of their measurement range, such results may be artefactual. Between 7.5–9 μm , the data is considered unreliable due to significant absorption by the beam splitter. Beyond 9 μm , the accuracy is highly dependent on the precise sample temperature, which was measured below the sample and may not reflect the actual surface temperature precisely.

Long-Wavelength Modulation Shifts

A further point of discussion concerns a shift in the modulation patterns observed in the 25–50 μm spectral region. Differences are noticeable between PTB, CAE, and CNR measurements. The explanation is the semi-transparency of the sample (thin coating on the not-transparent substrate) at these longer wavelengths, in combination with differing measurement geometries: CNR lab measurements were conducted at normal incidence; CAE used an 8° angle; PTB operated at 10°; CNR’s open-air measurements were taken at a 13.5° angle.

These varying geometries may cause the detectors to sample different effective optical paths through the sample, especially if partial transmission occurs at longer wavelengths.

4.3 V98RF

Figure 54: Directional spectral emissivities of the V98RF sample from 2.5 μm to 50 μm and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, LNE, CNR, PTB and DFM. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Figure 55: Directional spectral emissivities of the V98RF sample: enlarged view of the Fig. 54, from 6.7 μm to 50 μm measured by partners: CAE, LNE, CNR, PTB and DFM. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown

Figure 56: Hemispherical emissivities of the V98RF: measured by partners: LNE, NKUA, FIW, PTB and CAE. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Figure 57: Directional total emissivities of the V98RF sample measured by partners: PTB, IETccCSIC and CAE for the two angles of observation of 0/20° and 60° and for three wavelength ranges of 4 - 5 μm, 5 – 10.5 μm and 10.5 – 21 μm. The range of the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) for each individual measurement is shown.

Overview of Emissivity Results

In this dataset, notable discrepancies are observed between measurements, particularly in the modulation periods of the spectral emissivity curves (Figures 54–55). These differences are also evident in the hemispherical emissivity results, which exhibit the largest overall deviations among the three selected materials across the partner laboratories (Figure 56), as well as in the directional total emissivities (Figure 57).

Additionally, high discrepancies are evident at longer wavelengths (>10 μm), where emissivity values diverge more substantially.

Discussion of Contributing Factors

One key factor affecting all these results appears to be the coating thickness and the semitransparency of this coating on the non-transparent reflective substrate. Measurements conducted at PTB on samples of different diameters (50 mm and 90 mm), before distributed to the other partners, revealed noticeable differences in emissivity values (Fig. 58). This suggests that sample size, and potentially the associated edge effects or temperature uniformity, can significantly influence the measurements. In this context, the discrepancies seen in CNR’s results might be partly explained by their use of a considerably larger sample (150 mm diameter).

Differences in modulation patterns between datasets are also observed and may stem from several sources. Similar to the trends seen with the SPACECOOL sample, variations in the measurement angle can lead to detectable modulation shifts, particularly if the sample exhibits semi-transparency at longer wavelengths. These non-uniform or varying coating thicknesses across samples could affect the optical interference behavior, further contributing to the modulation differences. It should also be noted that the samples used for these measurements showed signs of surface scratching, which may contribute to variability in optical response.

These factors - geometry, sample condition, and coating thickness - must be carefully controlled or characterized to ensure consistency and comparability between emissivity measurements across different institutions.

Figure 58: Directional spectral emissivities of the V98RF sample batches measured at PTB: showing the difference in thicknesses, which leads to different measurement results

4.4 Conclusions for the IR range

The PaRaMetriC partners analysed a wide range of PRC materials, measuring directional, total and hemispherical emissivities using various techniques. The results showed reasonably good agreement, particularly within the atmospheric window region (7–13 μm) within the target uncertainty of 3%.

Discrepancies between measurements were also investigated, and several key influencing factors were identified:

Semi-transparency of materials, especially in the top layer, which can affect readings when placed over highly reflective substrates. Different techniques use different angles of observation.

Surface ageing and contamination, which can alter emissivity values over time.

Use of adhesives or thermal paste during sample mounting to the substrate, potentially introducing variability in the results.

Differences in measurement temperature, influencing both material properties and instrument response.

Outdoor measurements, which present additional challenges due to environmental variability and limited control over conditions.

For integrated total and hemispheric values, it is important to specify the wavelength range over which the integration or measurements were performed. PRC materials exhibit pronounced spectral characteristics, and variations in the selected range can lead to significant differences in the resulting values.

All these factors must be carefully considered when measuring the passive radiative cooling (PRC) performance of materials. It should be noted that all measurements in Section 4 were performed on three different materials, but the individual samples were manufactured for each partner according to the required geometry and size.

5 Comparative analysis in the Solar range

As stated at the beginning of Section 4, all measurements in the present section were performed on three selected benchmark materials SPACECOOL, V98RF and 3M R&D PRCF Foil, but the individual samples were manufactured for each partner according to the required geometry and size. All the partners used high-performance double beam spectrophotometers equipped with integrating spheres to measure the total reflectance (specular and diffuse components included) of the samples at near-normal incidence in the wavelength range of the solar radiation (250-2500 nm).

5.1 3M R&D PRCF Foil

Figure 59: Reflectance of the SPACECOOL sample in the solar range, from 250 nm to 2500 nm, and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, CSIC (IO), LNE, NKUA, TUBITAK, Aalto and RISE. Top - full range of reflectance; Bottom - zoom of the high reflectance range.

Figure 60: Reflectance of the SPACECOOL sample in the solar range, from 250 nm to 2500 nm, and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, CSIC (IO), LNE, NKUA, TUBITAK, Aalto and RISE. Zoom of the high reflectance range shown in Figure 59.

Overview of Reflectance in the solar range Results

Comparative measurements of reflectance in the solar range conducted by several partners generally show good agreement, but some discrepancies are observed:

- The low wavelength edge is similar for all the measurements, except in the TUBITAK spectra that show a shift to lower wavelengths
- A significant difference in reflectance in the visible range for wavelengths higher than 425 nm is observed between the results of different partners. The maximum difference in this range is around a 5% of reflectance between the measurements of CAE (around 99%) and TUBITAK (around 95% or lower).
- The spectra show a similar shape in the NIR range, with very prominent absorption bands. A shift of peak wavelength to higher values is observed in the spectra measured by CAE, while those measured by TUBITAK show a lower wavelength resolution.

Discussion of Measurement Uncertainties

Several factors can contribute to uncertainty in the reflectance comparison. First, some of the factors indicated in the case of emissivity measurements. These factors include differences in measurement geometry (as the specific light incidence angle) and differences in the samples due to inconsistency in the use of the thermal paste during the 3M foil mounting to the aluminium substrate or due to surface contamination and material aging.

Regarding those factors specific for the solar range measurements, the methodology followed by each partner for the correction for 100 % and for zero signal, might also have an influence, but it is not expected to explain

the significant differences observed in the high reflectance region. Other sources of variations between different partners that may have a higher impact are related to measurement difficulties in the case of high reflectance samples, as is the case for PRC materials. More precisely, the difficulty to adequately calibrate the measured signal when the reflectance of the sample under analysis is close to the reflectance of the reference sample. This factor might explain differences in wavelength regions with high reflectance, as observed in Figures 59-60 for wavelengths around 600 nm. Another factor influencing the results in the case of PRC materials, with specific compositions and surface morphologies, may be the orientation of the sample with respect to the light beam. Depending on the sample surface features, rotating the sample with respect to the beam may give rise to differences in the optical response that may account for part of the discrepancies observed in Figures 59-60.

5.2 SPACECOOL

Figure 61: Reflectance of the SPACECOOL sample in the solar range, from 250 nm to 2500 nm, and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, CSIC (IO), LNE, NKUA, TUBITAK, Aalto and RISE.

Figure 62: Reflectance of the SPACECOOL sample in the solar range, from 250 nm to 2500 nm, and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, CSIC (IO), LNE, NKUA, TUBITAK, Aalto and RISE. Zoom of the high reflectance range shown in Figure 61.

Overview of Reflectance in the solar range Results

Comparative analysis of reflectance spectra in the solar range collected in Figure 61 shows a similar low wavelength absorption edge and a similar spectral shape along the whole wavelength range in the measurements conducted by the different partners. A shift to higher wavelengths in the NIR absorption peaks is observed in the spectrum measured by CAE, as already noticed in the case of 3M foil (section 5.1). However, the main discrepancies are observed in the reflectance values obtained for wavelengths higher than the low wavelength edge. While the reflectance values measured by CAE in the visible range are around 98-99 %, those measured by TUBITAK are around 90-91% and the rest of the partners obtain values in between these two limits.

Discussion of Measurement Uncertainties

The factors identified in section 5.1 as possibly contributing to uncertainty in the 3M foil are also valid to account for part of the differences observed in the measurements of the SPACECOOL sample. However, the differences in reflectance between the partners are significantly higher in this case, suggesting that the sources of uncertainty related to the sample (such as aging and surface features) may be increasing the uncertainty in the case of the SPACECOOL results.

5.3 V98RF

Figure 63: Reflectance of the V98RF sample in the solar range, from 250 nm to 2500 nm, and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, CSIC (IO), LNE, NKUA, TUBITAK, Aalto and RISE.

Figure 64: Reflectance of the V98RF sample in the solar range, from 250 nm to 2500 nm, and at an angle close to normal measured by partners: CAE, CSIC (IO), LNE, NKUA, TUBITAK, Aalto and RISE. Zoom of the high reflectance range shown in Figure 63.

Overview of Reflectance in the solar range Results

Comparative analysis of reflectance spectra in the solar range for the V98RF sample indicates a shift of the short wavelength edge to lower wavelengths in the TUBITAK spectra with respect to other partners. The differences in reflectance are lower in this case than those observed for the 3M foil and the SPACECOOL sample. In fact, the highest difference in the visible range (for wavelengths higher than the absorption edge) is around a 3% of reflectance, again between the lowest reflectance measured by TUBITAK (around 95-96%) and the highest by CAE (around 98-99%). However, significant discrepancies are observed in this case in the NIR range with clear fringes appearing in the spectra obtained by LNE, CAE and NKUA, overlapping with weak absorption bands. The spectra measured by CISC show some fringes, but only in the high wavelength range, while the TUBITAK spectra do not show fringes and show more intense absorption bands. Finally, one of the samples measured by Aalto shows clear fringes, and the other presents a smooth curve with no fringes.

Discussion of Measurement Uncertainties

The factors identified in section 5.1 as possibly contributing to uncertainty in the 3M foil are also valid to account for the uncertainty in the case of the V98RF sample. However, the influence of the specific composition and/or surface morphology of this sample is observed to reduce the discrepancies in the reflectance values for wavelengths higher than the low wavelength absorption edge. At the same time these specific features of the sample are observed to give rise to the appearance of fringes in the spectra.

5.4 Conclusions for the Solar range

The PaRaMetriC partners analysed a wide range of PRC materials measuring the total reflectance at near normal incidence in the solar radiation wavelength range (from 250 nm to 2500 nm) with high-performance double beam spectrophotometers, equipped with integrating spheres.

The differences observed in the reflectance spectra obtained by different partners are higher than expected from variations in the measurement geometry (as the specific light incidence angle) or in the methodology followed by each partner for the correction for 100 % and for zero signal. Part of these differences may be related to the specific properties of PRC materials. Specifically, to their high reflectance values, close to or even higher than the reflectance of the usual reflectance references, and also to their novel composition and surface morphology optimized for their unique optical response.

In addition, a significant impact on the observed discrepancies may come from differences between the samples measured by each partner, related to the samples preparation and to their possible surface contamination and material aging.

In order to separate the factors affecting the measurement uncertainty and for a better understanding of the reason for the observed discrepancies, all the PRC samples measured by the partners have been collected by the CSIC to be measured with the same equipment and under the same conditions. An analysis is under performance to clarify the impact on the spectral response of factors as beam polarization and sample orientation with respect to the light beam.

6 Conclusions

In the WP3, the PaRaMetriC partners performed systematic intercomparisons of reflectance and emittance measurements of PRC materials across the spectral range 0.25 μm – 50 μm . Each partner characterized at least one sample of the three selected PRC materials with their respective instruments, provided uncertainty budgets.

In the solar spectral range (250 nm – 2500 nm):

- CAE and LNE used integrating sphere setups.
- RISE calculated solar absorption from total reflectance measurements with a spectrophotometer equipped with an integrating sphere (250 nm – 2500 nm) and performed BRDF measurements.
- TUBITAK applied robot-based absolute reflectance and integrating-sphere reflectance measurement systems.
- CSIC contributed with a fibre optic portable UV–VIS–NIR spectrometer and measured BRDF at different incidence and observation angles.
- NKUA used an advanced UV/VIS/NIR spectrophotometer with an integrating sphere to determine solar absorptance according to ASTM E903.
- Aalto measured BRDF with its reference 3D gonireflectometer and horizontal sample holder.

In the infrared spectral range (2.5 μm – 50 μm):

- CAE Bayern and LNE used integrating sphere setups.
- LNE and PTB employed their reference emissivity setups.
- LNE and FIW measured total near-normal emissivity using the commercial TIR100-2 emissometer, previously characterised in EMPIR project 16NRM06 EMIRIM.
- CNR applied the FIRMOS instrument for spectral emissivity measurements.
- DFM used their reference setup for angular-resolved emissivity.
- CSIC contributed with a portable emissometer.
- RISE used its reflectance measurement setup.
- NKUA determined total hemispherical emittance according to ASTM C1371 with an AE Model emissometer.

The intercomparison of reference and end-user techniques for reflectance and emittance measurements of PRC materials in the spectral range from 0.25 μm to 50 μm demonstrated overall good consistency between partners, particularly within the IR atmospheric window region (8–13 μm), where results generally fell within the target uncertainty of 3%. At the same time, several sources of discrepancies were identified, including the semi-transparent nature of certain PRC layers, surface ageing and contamination, sample preparation and mounting, measurement temperature, and the inherent challenges of outdoor testing.

In the solar spectral range (0.25–2.5 μm), higher than expected differences were observed in the reflectance spectra obtained by different partners. These discrepancies were attributed not only to methodological factors (e.g. corrections for baseline signals or measurement geometry), but also to the unique optical properties of PRC materials, whose high reflectance values approach or exceed those of conventional reflectance standards, and to variations in sample preparation and ageing effects. A coordinated follow-up measurement campaign on identical samples under controlled conditions is ongoing to disentangle the impact of sample characteristics and instrumental factors. As this campaign was conducted in addition to the tasks of WP3 and

includes both microscopic examination of the sample structure and tests of the dependence of results on the sample's horizontal and vertical orientation relative to the incident radiation, the corresponding measurements will be published at a later stage.

This work package also included investigations of long-term durability of PRC materials, focusing on changes in optical properties under environmental influences such as heat, moisture, contamination, and aging.

It should also be noted that, beyond the three candidate PRC materials highlighted here, a broader set of samples was studied in the course of the project to strengthen the overall validation and to capture the diversity of potential PRC designs.

Overall, the study confirms the suitability of the measurement techniques of the PaRaMetriC partners for reliable characterisation of PRC materials, while also highlighting the critical importance of sample preparation, handling, and clear definition of measurement conditions (geometry, wavelength integration range, and environment). These findings provide a validated basis for establishing traceability of measurements, improving the calibration of portable in-field instruments, and ensuring robust evaluation of PRC performance in practical applications.

7 References

- [1] A. Synnefa, A. Pantazaras, M. Santamouris, E. Bozonnet, M. Doya, M. Zinzi, A. Muscio, A. Libbra, C. Ferrari, V. Coccia, F. Rossi, D. Kolokotsa, Interlaboratory comparison of cool roofing material measurement methods Proceedings of the 34th AIVC - 3rd TightVent - 2nd Cool Roofs' - 1st venticool Conference , 25-26 September, Athens 2013
- [2] W. Tong, et al. "A structural polymer for highly efficient all-day passive radiative cooling." *Nature communications* 12.1 (2021): 1-11
- [3] I. Müller, A. Adibekyan, B. Gutschwager, E. Kononogova, S. König, C. Monte, M. Reiniger and J. Hollandt. Calibration capabilities at PTB for radiation thermometry, quantitative thermography and emissivity. *DGZfP-Berichtsband BB*, 167, 2018, 329 – 333. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21611/qirt.2018.015>
- [4] C. Monte and J. Hollandt. "The Measurement of Directional Spectral Emissivity in the Temperature Range from 80 °C to 400 °C at the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt." *High Temperatures - High Pressures*, 2010, 39, 151-164
- [5] A. Adibekyan, C. Monte, C., M. Kehrt, B. Gutschwager and J. Hollandt. "Emissivity Measurement Under Vacuum from 4 µm to 100 µm and from -40 °C to 450 °C at PTB." *International J. Thermophys.* 2015, 36, 283-289, doi:10.1007/s10765-014-1745-7
- [6] C. Pachot et al., in *International Conference on Space Optics - ICSO 2020*, 11852, 904-917, 2021, doi:10.1117/12.2599355
- [7] M.Z. Hakuba, P. Pilewskie, G. Stephens and the Libera Science Team: Libera – Observing and Understanding Earth's Energy Budget, *EGU General Assembly 2021*, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-13961, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-13961>, 2021
- [8] L. Hanssen et al., *Metrologia*, 53, 3001, 2016
- [9] R.B. Pérez-Sáez, L. Campo and M.J.Tello. Analysis of the Accuracy of Methods for the Direct Measurement of Emissivity. *International Journal of Thermophysics*. Vol. 29, 3, pp. 1141-1155
- [10] A. Adibekyan, E. Kononogova, C. Monte, et al. Review of PTB Measurements on Emissivity, Reflectivity and Transmissivity of Semitransparent Fiber-Reinforced Plastic Composites, *Int J Thermophys* 40, 36 (2019)
- [11] E. Goldstein, A. Raman & S. Fan. Sub-ambient non-evaporative fluid cooling with the sky. *Nat Energy* 2, 17143 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nenergy.2017.143>
- [12] J. Hameury, B. Hay, JR. Filtz. Measurement of total hemispherical emissivity using a calorimetric technique. *Int J Thermophys* 28:1607 (2007)
- [13] Belotti, C.; Barbara, F.; Barucci, M.; Bianchini, G.; D'Amato, F.; Del Bianco, S.; Di Natale, G.; Gai, M.; Montori, A.; Pratesi, F.; et al. The Far-Infrared Radiation Mobile Observation System (FIRMOS) for spectral characterization of the atmospheric emission. *Atmos. Meas. Tech.* 2023, 16, 2511–2529.
- [14] Palchetti, L., Barucci, M., Belotti, C., Bianchini, G., Cluzet, B., D'Amato, F., Del Bianco, S., Di Natale, G., Gai, M., Khordakova, D., Montori, A., Oetjen, H., Rettinger, M., Rolf, C., Schuettmeyer, D., Sussmann, R., Viciani, S., Vogelmann, H., and Wienhold, F. G.: Observations of the downwelling far-infrared atmospheric emission at the Zugspitze observatory, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 13, 4303–4312, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-4303-2021>, 2021.
- [15] Bliankinshtein N.; Nguyen C.; Ranjbar K.; Borque P.; Nichman L.; Bala K.; Huang Y.; Liu L.; Riot Bretcher B.; Bigras E.; Brindley H.; Murray J.; Mariani Z.; Blanchet J.-P.; Blanchard Y.; Loftus A.; Barucci M.; Belotti C.; Bianchini G.; Palchetti L.; Viciani S.; Warwick L.; Oetjen H.; Schuettmeyer D. W-band, HiSRAMS, AERI, FIRR-2, FINESSE and FIRMOS Experiment on Remote Sensing (WHAFFERS): multi-frequency, multi-platform campaign overview. *Living Planet Symposium June 2025*.

- [16] Belotti, C.; Barucci, M.; Bianchini, G.; D'Amato, F.; Del Bianco, S.; Di Natale, G.; Dinelli B. M.; Ridolfi, M.; Viciani S.; Palchetti, L. The Far-Infrared Radiation Mobile Observation System (FIRMOS), characterization of the measurements and retrieval studies. AGU Annual Meeting Dec 2024.
- [17] Di Natale, G.; Belotti, C.; Barucci, M.; Ridolfi, M.; Viciani, S.; D'Amato, F.; Del Bianco, S.; Dinelli, B.M.; Palchetti, L. Retrieval of Cloud, Atmospheric, and Surface Properties from Far-Infrared Spectral Radiances Measured by FIRMOS-B During the 2022 HEMERA Stratospheric Balloon Campaign. *Remote Sens.* 2025, 17, 2458. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs17142458>
- [18] Bianchini, G. and Palchetti, L.: Technical Note: REFIR-PAD level 1 data analysis and performance characterization, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 8, 3817–3826, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-8-3817-2008>, 2008.
- [19](1) Clough, S. A.; Shephard, M. W.; Mlawer, E. J.; Delamere, J. S.; Iacono, M. J.; Cady-Pereira, K.; Boukabara, S.; Brown, P. D. Atmospheric Radiative Transfer Modeling: A Summary of the AER Codes. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer* 2005, 91 (2), 233–244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2004.05.058>.
- [20] (1) Bellisario, C.; Brindley, H. E.; Murray, J. E.; Last, A.; Pickering, J.; Harlow, R. C.; Fox, S.; Fox, C.; Newman, S. M.; Smith, M.; Anderson, D.; Huang, X.; Chen, X. Retrievals of the Far Infrared Surface Emissivity Over the Greenland Plateau Using the Tropospheric Airborne Fourier Transform Spectrometer (TAFTS). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 2017, 122 (22), 12,152–12,166. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JD027328>.
- [21] S. Clausen, *Int J Thermophys* (2007) 28:2145–2154
- [22] M. Battuello, S. Clausen, J. Hameury, P. Bloembergen, in *Proceedings of TEMPMEKO 1999, 7th International Symposium on Temperature and Thermal Measurements in Industry and Science*, ed. by J.F. Dubbeldam, M.J. de Groot (Edauw Johannissen bv, Delft, 1999), pp. 601–606
- [23] INGLAS GmbH: „TIRprinciples“. <https://inglas.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/TIRprinciples.png>. last accessed on 29.08.2025.
- [24] Inglas GmbH & Co.KG: <https://inglas.org/tir100/> (last access: 26 January 2021).
- [25] 2 E. Kononogova, A. Adibekyan, C. Monte, and J. Hollandt, “Characterization, calibration and validation of an industrial emissometer” *Journal of Sensors and Sensor Systems*, 2019, 8, 233–242. doi.org/10.5194/jsss-8-233-2019
- [26] 3 J. Hameury, G. Failleau, M. Arduini, J. Manara, E. Kononogova, A. Adibekyan, C. Monte, A. Kirmes, E. Palacio, H. Simon, “Assessment of uncertainties for measurements of total near-normal emissivity of low emissivity foils with an industrial emissometer”. Submitted to *Journal of Sensors and Sensor Systems*, November 2020.
- [27] European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR), Improvement of Emissivity Measurements on Reflective Insulation Materials (EMIRIM), Grant Agreement No. 16NRM06. [Online]. Available: <http://projects.inne.eu/jrp-emirim/> (last access: 29 September 2023)
- [28] Q-Lab Technical Bulletin LU-8009. QUV & Q-SUN Ein Vergleich zwischen zwei effizienten Methoden für Schnellbewitterungs- und Lichtbeständigkeitstests. <https://www.q-lab.com/documents/public/b024a7e1-18ee-4528-b459-d7d23ddea271.pdf>
- [29] EOTA Technical Report. Exposure procedure for artificial weathering. EOTA TR010, Edition May 2004
- [30] S. Nevas, F. Manoocheri and E. Ikonen, "Gonioreflectometer for measuring spectral diffuse reflectance," *Applied Optics*, vol. 43, no. 35, pp. 6391-6399, 2004.
- [31] D. Lanevski, F. Manoocheri and E. Ikonen, "Gonioreflectometer for measuring 3D spectral BRDF of horizontally aligned samples with traceability to SI," *Metrologia*, vol. 59, no. 2, p. 025006, 2022.
- [32] S. Holopainen and F. Manoocheri, "Comparison measurements of 0: 45 radiance factor and goniometrically determined diffuse reflectance," *Applied Optics*, vol. 48, no. 15, pp. 2946-2956, 2009.